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A psychoacoustic sonification design for monitoring preterm infants via pulse oximetry

MASTERTHESIS

submitted by: Sebastian Schwarz

1. Supervisor: Prof. Dr. Rolf Bader
2. Supervisor: Dr. phil. Tim Ziemer

Institute of Systematic Musicology

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Abstract

Sonifications of conventional pulse oximeters do not inform the listener with sufficient accuracy whether the oxygen saturation (SpO_2) is in a range between 90- and 95%, which is recommended for premature infants. In the present study a novel sonification was developed for monitoring preterm infants with a pulse oximeter, whereby the sound design is based on findings from the field of psychoacoustics. In an online listening test the participants' ability to identify SpO_2 ranges and to estimate absolute SpO_2 values was tested. Results show that participants identify the SpO_2 ranges significantly more accurately with the novel psychoacoustic sonification than with the conventional sonification. The results also indicate that absolute SpO_2 values are estimated more accurately with the psychoacoustic than with the conventional sonification. Therefore, the psychoacoustic sonification may improve a clinician's ability to monitor SpO_2 in the case of preterm infants. Moreover, the results underline the usefulness of considering psychoacoustic principles in the sound design of sonifications. Based on the results, further modifications of the psychoacoustic sound design are discussed. In addition, the present study explored the influence of different covariates on the success in the listening test. Participants were questioned regarding their musicality, their experience with pulse oximeters and their experience with the interpretation of sounds. No significant effect is found for any of the covariates, while possible reasons are discussed. Furthermore, the present study explored aesthetic aspects of sonifications. An alternative sonification was developed, whereby the perceived pleasantness was taken into account during the sound design. All sonifications were evaluated by the participants with regard to aesthetic aspects. The results show that it is important to consider both the perceived pleasantness and the context of use when designing a sonification.

Yes,
perfect: The
concrete result and
its implication for
the field in
general!

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1 Introduction

Sonifications are used in a wide variety of fields, including bio-medicine, assistance to visually impaired people, data mining and exploration, seismology, sport activities, computer interaction, art and many others (Hermann, Hunt, & Neuhoff, 2011). Accordingly the research field of sonification is interdisciplinary by nature. To create a successful sonification, the input of a diverse area of disciplines is necessary. These include acoustics, psychology, psychoacoustics, sound engineering, musicology and cognitive science (Hermann et al., 2011). Sonifications use sounds to convey information about data to the listener, in order to facilitate their interpretation. Providing information in the auditory modality has great potential, as the human auditory system is very complex and powerful (Hermann et al., 2011). This can be seen, for example, in its ability to recognize patterns. Even in an environment with a lot of background noise, spoken words can usually be recognized (Hermann et al., 2011). Moreover, complex auditory scenes can be processed seemingly effortless. At an orchestra concert, the ear is exposed to a mixture of sounds with a variety of different sources. Nevertheless, the auditory system is able to identify individual instruments or melody lines and thus to organize the auditory scene into distinct objects of perception. Furthermore, "auditory perception is particularly sensitive to temporal characteristics, or changes in sounds over time" (Kramer et al., 1999, p. 5). The communication of information through the auditory modality is therefore suitable for monitoring temporally complex information (Kramer et al., 1999). In fact, according to Vickers (2011) "process monitoring would seem to be one of those tasks that was born to be sonified" (p. 455).

The sonification of a pulse oximeter has been developed so that the listener has to continuously be aware of changes in oxygen saturation. **some use pure tones, but many use complex tones** Conventional pulse oximeters produce a pulse-sonification that is synchronized with the heartbeat and has a frequency, which is a function of the instantaneous oxygen saturation. However, several studies have shown that it is difficult to maintain the oxygen saturation in a certain target range using sonifications of conventional pulse oximeters. Particularly in premature infants, a deviation from the target range can have serious consequences for health. In a study by Schwarz and Ziemer (2019) a novel sonification for the pulse oximeter was developed to provide the listener with relevant information about the oxygen saturation in the case of premature infants. The present work is based on the study by Schwarz and Ziemer (2019), whereas the sonification was further developed and modified (see chapter 1.3 for details). Moreover, no control group was used in the study by Schwarz and Ziemer (2019). This issue was addressed in the present study, by including the sonification of a conventional pulse oximeter.

In the present study a particular focus is placed on psychoacoustic principles for the

development of the sonifications. It is assumed, that otherwise information provided in the auditory modality cannot be conveyed to the listener in a predictable and reliable way. In the following chapters, the field of psychoacoustics and the concept of sonification are discussed. Conventional sonifications as well as novel approaches of sonifications in the field of pulse oximetry are addressed. Subsequently, the sonifications developed in the present study are introduced. These include a conventional and two novel sonifications, specifically the psychoacoustic sonification, based on Schwarz and Ziemer (2019) and an additional alternative sonification. Finally, the sonifications were compared with each other in an online listening test, examining both functional and aesthetic aspects.

1.1 Psychoacoustics

Listening is a complex task, as there are typically a large number of sounds which are overlapping in time and frequency. The hearing system is then stimulated by a signal of pressure fluctuations, which is the result of the combination of all simultaneously occurring sounds (Carlile, 2011). “Psychoacoustics is the translation of physical sound input to auditory perception” (Ziemer, 2020, p. 65), whereas the task of auditory perception is to process the sensory input and to build a representation of reality (Bregman, 1990). An important part of auditory perception is the construction of separate mental descriptions of the different sound-generating events in the environment. This is the fundamental problem of what Bregman (1990) calls auditory scene analysis. Auditory perception is not only based on the physical properties of sound, but also on the listening context and the individual (Ziemer, 2020, p. 65). Therefore, an essential part of psychoacoustics refers to the relationships between acoustic stimuli and hearing sensations, which allow a high generalizability to other persons and situations and form the basis of auditory perception (Ziemer, 2020, p. 65). This chapter first describes the processing of auditory stimuli at the sensational level. Here, topics that are particularly relevant for the development of the sonifications of the present study are discussed. Subsequently this chapter deals with auditory scene analysis, where sensations are further processed to form mental representations.

1.1.1 Human ear and auditory pathway

The following is a brief overview of the anatomy and processing of sound in the auditory system. The auditory system consists of the outer, middle and inner ears, as well as the auditory nerve and the central auditory pathways (Gelfand, 2009, p. 20). The visible part of the outer ear is called the pinna (auricle). It consists mainly of elastic cartilage covered with skin (Ziemer, 2020, p. 50). Besides capturing sound, it also serves as a filter that amplifies or attenuates different frequencies depending on the angle of incidence (Ziemer, 2020, p. 50). The ear canal is the connecting

Figure 1. Basic structure of an uncoiled cochlear. The oval window and the round window are located in the scala vestibuli and the scala tympani respectively. These scalae are filled with perilymph and are separated by the scala media, which is filled with endolymph. From Ziemer (2020), p. 52.

piece between pinna and ear drum (Gelfand, 2009, p. 23). It has a S-shaped form and is about 3 cm long. Similar to the pinna it has a filtering function, amplifying frequencies around 4 kHz (Ziemer, 2020, p. 50). At the end of the ear canal lies the eardrum. It consists of a thin membrane (0.074 mm thin) with an elliptical shape (diameter: 0.8-1 cm) and is connected to the ossicular chain (Ziemer, 2020, p. 50). The ossicles transmit the deflections of the eardrum to the inner ear (Gelfand, 2009, p. 27). They are called malleus (hammer), incus (anvil) and stapes (stirrup) and form the ossicular chain (Gelfand, 2009, p. 27). The malleus is attached to the eardrum and on the other side of the ossicular chain the stapes is attached to the oval window (Gelfand, 2009, pp. 27-28). In combination the outer and middle ear amplify a signal by a factor of about 30. This is achieved by the resonance of the ear canal and the impedance conversion of the ossicular chain (Ziemer, 2020, p. 50).

The cochlear consists of three chambers or scalae, which extend from the base to the apex and are filled with fluid (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 25). The stapes causes a displacement of the oval window, which is equalized at the so-called round window (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 25). In Figure 1 the structure of the inner ear is illustrated. The three chambers are called scala vestibuli, scala media and scala tympani (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 26). As can be seen in Figure 1 the oval window lies within the scala vestibuli and its fluid is therefore in direct contact with the stapes. Scala vestibuli and scala media are separated by a membrane, called Reissner's membrane (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 25). As this membrane is very thin, it becomes negligible from a hydromechanical perspective. The basilar membrane on the other side separates the scala media from the scala tympani (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 25). The fluid found in scala vestibuli and scala tympani is called perilymph and in the scala media it is called endolymph. As the perilymph has a high sodium content and the endolymph has a high potassium content, the scala media has a positive electric potential of

80 mV (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 26). The cochlear has the shape of a spiral with 2,5 turns. This way the basilar membrane can have a length of about 32 mm (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 26). The mechanical oscillations are converted into neuronal signals in the organ of Corti. The organ of Corti is located on the basilar membrane and contains supporting cells and the hair cells (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 26). A distinction is made between inner and outer hair cells. There are one row of inner hair cells and three rows of outer hair cells (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 26). The outer hair cells are partially attached through sensory hair cells called stereocilia to the tectorial membrane, which lies on top of the organ of Corti (Ziemer, 2020, p. 52). A traveling wave is created by movements of the oval window and moves along the basilar membrane. Its amplitude increases gradually up to a maximum in a certain area and decreases quickly behind it (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 28). The area of maximum vibration depends on the frequency of the traveling wave. This form of frequency separation via the location on the basilar membrane is called the place principle (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 29). At the oval window the displacement of the basilar membrane is at its maximum for high frequencies. The lower the frequency, the greater the distance between the oval window and the maximum displacement of the basilar membrane (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 29). The so-called characteristic frequency of a certain location on the basilar membrane describes the frequency at which the excitation is maximum (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 31). The hair cells are only sensitive to positive deflections (Ziemer, 2020, p. 52). The relative displacement of the tectorial membrane to the basilar membrane leads to a shearing of the hair cells and thus to the opening and closing of transduction channels and finally to a neural fire at the auditory nerve (Ziemer, 2020, p. 52). The main function of the 3500 inner hair cells is the detection of these relative displacements of the tectorial membrane (Ziemer, 2020, p. 53). They are connected to approximately 30 000 neurons, which are located in the auditory nerve (Ziemer, 2020, p. 53). Neurons that get input from hair cells in a particular area of the basilar membrane are most sensitive to the frequency of the traveling wave reaching its peak amplitude in this area. This frequency is called best frequency of the neuron (Ziemer, 2020, p. 53).

In the following, the main stages of the auditory pathway are described in a short and simplified form (see e.g. Gelfand, 2009, p. 20 for further details). The main stages of the auditory pathway for each side of the hearing system include in a hierarchical order the cochlear nucleus, the superior olive, the inferior colliculus (IC), the thalamus and the auditory cortex (Felix, Gourévitch, & Portfors, 2018). Along the auditory pathway numerous connections within a hemisphere (ipsilateral), between hemispheres (contralateral), as well as connections to both hemispheres (bilateral) can be observed (Ziemer, 2020, p. 54). The afferent auditory pathway refers to synapses, which either lead to structures on the same or an higher stage along the auditory pathway. In the other direction, from higher to lower stages

along the central nervous system, one speaks of efferent connections (Ziemer, 2020, p. 54).

The spatial distribution of frequencies on the basilar membrane is preserved in the auditory nerve fibres, which innervate the cochlear nuclei (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 59). The area on the basilar membrane, where a neuron innervates an inner hair cell, determines the best frequency of this neuron. Maintaining the spatial arrangement of different frequencies in the nerve fibres and higher processing stages of the auditory pathway is called tonotopic organization (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 59). For the localization of a sound source it is necessary to exchange information between the two ears. This is already done at early stages of the auditory pathway by comparing the intensity, phase and latency of the signals (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 59). Interaural level differences are analyzed in the cochlear nuclei and interaural time differences in the superior olivary complex (Ziemer, 2020, p. 57). Along the afferent auditory pathway, the response behavior of nerve cells becomes more complex and shows an increasing specialization. Depending on the nerve cell, a response to different signals, such as interaural delays, level differences between the ears, frequency modulation or changes in amplitude, can be observed (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 59). In general phase locking and processing speed decreases along the ascending auditory pathway, while the number of neurons involved increases sharply (Schneider, 2018, p. 625). The extraction of many sound features is already achieved at the stage of the midbrain. Here neurons of the inferior colliculus (IC) integrate signals of several ascending paths from the brain stem (Felix et al., 2018). Therefore, a large part of the auditory analysis does not require conscious analysis (Ziemer, 2020, p. 60). The thalamus can be seen as a kind of gate that lets important information pass on its way to the cortex and filters out unimportant information (Ziemer, 2020, p. 58). After the thalamus, the information is further processed in the auditory cortex and other cortical auditory areas (Ziemer, 2020, p. 58).

One example of efferents in the auditory system concerns its dynamic range. For normal speech with a sound pressure level of about 60 dB_{SPL} the displacement of the basilar membrane is in the range of tenth of nanometers (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 31). However the human hearing system is sensitive to tones with sound pressure 1000 times smaller (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 31). For very low sound pressure levels the sensitivity of our hearing system is much larger, than what could be expected from extrapolating from higher levels. This is achieved by active nonlinear feedback of the hearing system, which can provide an additional gain of up to 30 dB_{SPL} (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 33). It is assumed that the reason for this increased sensitivity lies in an interaction between outer and inner hair cells. The stereocilia, which sit on top of the outer hair cells, can change their length and thus influence the deflection of the basilar membrane (Ziemer, 2020, p. 60). For a high sound pressure level the deflection of the basilar membrane can be reduced and for a low sound pressure

level probably increased. Thus the auditory system achieves a dynamic range of more than 100 dB_{SPL}, although the inner hair cell range lies only between 40 and 60 dB_{SPL} (Ziemer, 2020, pp. 60-61). The auditory system is therefore not a passive receiver, but influences the processing of the sensory input via an active control.

1.1.2 Hearing area

The hearing area can be illustrated as a plane (see Figure 2) within which sounds are audible (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 17). In Figure 2 on the abscissa the logarithm of the frequency and on the ordinate the sound pressure level and the sound intensity level is used. Sounds are usually described as a temporal change in sound pressure. The unit of sound pressure is Pascal (Pa). As the hearing area covers a range of sound pressures between 10^{-5} Pa and 10^2 Pa, a logarithmic unit called sound pressure level is used to deal with such a broad range (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 1). It is defined as follows:

$$L = 20 \log\left(\frac{p}{p_0}\right) \text{ dB}, \quad (1)$$

where $p_0 = 20\mu$ Pa is a reference value of sound pressure (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 1). The sound intensity level is defined as:

$$L = 10 \log\left(\frac{I}{I_0}\right) \text{ dB} = 20 \log\left(\frac{p}{p_0}\right) \text{ dB}, \quad (2)$$

where I_0 is a reference value defined as 10^{-12} W/m^2 (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 1).

Figure 2. The hearing area is located between the threshold in quiet and the threshold of pain. Furthermore, the areas that are occupied by music and speech are highlighted, as well as a limit of damage risk. The dotted line of the threshold in quiet originates from people, who regularly listen to very loud music. From Fastl & Zwicker (2007), p. 17.

The hearing area covers a frequency range from 20 Hz to 20 kHz (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 18). It is confined by the threshold in quiet for low levels and by the threshold of pain for high levels, whereas the limits provided in Figure 2 are valid for pure tones with a duration for more than about 100 ms. As can be seen in the illustration, music occupies a large part of the hearing area with an intensity, that ranges from 20 dB_{SPL} to 95 dB_{SPL} (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 18). The threshold in quiet is the sound pressure level at which a pure tone is just audible (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 19). Figure 2 shows that the threshold in quiet depends on the frequency of the tone. For low frequencies the threshold in quiet is reached for comparatively high sound pressure levels, as for 20 Hz a sound pressure level of about 70 dB_{SPL} is required. For higher frequencies the threshold in quiet decreases steadily, reaching its lowest sound pressure levels between 2 and 5 kHz, where the human auditory system is very sensitive and even negative sound pressure levels can be observed (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 20). Above 12 kHz the hearing threshold increases strongly and reaches a limit between 16 and 18 kHz. Beyond this limit, even high sound pressure levels can no longer cause sensation (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 20).

1.1.3 Pitch

In many languages the term pitch refers to a particular property of sound that can be described on a vertical dimension that ranges from low to high. In a narrow sense, the perception of pitch refers to sounds that are quasiperiodic and have an approximately harmonic spectrum (Schneider, 2018, p. 606). An example of a pitch scale is the so-called mel scale. It is based on measurements where participants were asked to double or halve the pitch of a reference pure tone by changing the frequency of a second pure tone. Accordingly, doubling the value on the mel scale corresponds to a perceived doubling of pitch (see Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, pp. 111-113). The mel scale shows that the perception of pitch is rather logarithmic than linear in nature. According to the mel scale, increasing or decreasing the frequency of a pure tone below 500 Hz exponentially is perceived as an approximately linear change of pitch (see Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p.112).

For a pure tone, the perceived pitch is essentially determined by its frequency. The frequency is represented by a redundant coding of tonotopic organization of the basilar membrane and the auditory nerve fibres and the so-called best frequency of the neurons (Ziemer, 2020, p. 74). A traveling wave with a low frequency also leads to a deflection of the basilar membrane in areas of high frequencies. There exist several mechanisms, which ensure that low frequency tones are not perceived as a broad band sound. The auditory system is able to locate the peak of the traveling wave and uses an amplification of the neural firing in the corresponding region (Ziemer, 2020, p. 74). Moreover, it ensures that the neural activity in other regions

remains relatively low (Ziemer, 2020, p. 74). This is achieved as the displacement of the basilar membrane is relatively low, compared to the peak region and the neurons response is relatively weak, if the traveling waves frequency does not match the best frequency of the neurons (Ziemer, 2020, p. 74). In addition the auditory system actively suppresses the neural activity of these neurons (Ziemer, 2020, p. 74). The neuronal activity pattern in the auditory nerve also reflects the period of the stimulus (Schneider, 2018, p. 607). This is achieved as the neurons fire in phase with the traveling wave. More precisely, in phase with the positive deflection of the traveling wave, as they respond only to elongations along one direction (Ziemer, 2020, p. 56). Although a single neuron is not reliable in preserving the phase, the sum of several neurons shows peaks of neural activity, which are in phase with the traveling wave and encode its frequency (Ziemer, 2020, p. 56). Since the neurons have a certain refractory time, this form of coding only works for frequencies below 1 kHz. Above 4 kHz neither frequency nor phase are adequately represented (Ziemer, 2020, p. 57). Therefore, essentially the amplitude is transmitted via this coding form (Ziemer, 2020, p. 57). Besides frequency, there are other parameters that influence pitch, albeit to a lesser extent. One example is the sound pressure level. At a frequency of 200 Hz an increase of the sound pressure level of a pure tone from 40 dB_{SPL} to 80 dB_{SPL} leads to a decrease in pitch (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 113). The reserved effect can be found at a frequency of 6 kHz, where a sound pressure level of 80 dB_{SPL} results in a higher pitch than a sound pressure level of 40 dB_{SPL} (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 113).

The sum of several pure tones results in a complex tone. If the frequencies of these pure tones are also integer multiples of the fundamental frequency, one speaks of a harmonic complex tone (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 119). "Although complex tones contain many pure tones, they . . . produce . . . one single or perhaps one prominent pitch" (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 119). For a harmonic tone this corresponds to its fundamental frequency (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 119). Participants can usually assign the pitch of a sinusoidal tone to the pitch of a harmonic complex tone, as long as the fundamental frequency is within a range typical of speech and music (Schneider, 2018, p. 607). However, for frequencies below 1 kHz the corresponding pure tone can show a frequency difference of almost 3% (producing the same pitch at a lower frequency as the corresponding complex tone) (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 119). In a harmonic complex tone, there are several partial tones that are coded via the basilar membrane. The information about its pitch can be obtained from the fundamental frequency as well as from the other partials (Schneider, 2018, p. 607). The octaves in particular contribute to a stronger perception of the fundamental frequency (Schneider, 2018, p. 607). As for sine tones the periodicity for complex tones is also coded in the neuronal signal. A harmonic complex tone, whose partial tones are in phase, thus shows several hints that allow a perception of pitch (Schneider,

2018, p. 607). Besides the partial tones and the period of the signal, this includes the decreasing amplitude for the partial tones with an increasing harmonic number (Schneider, 2018, p. 607). As for pure tones, the pitch for harmonic complex tones shows a dependence on level (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 120). The so-called residue pitch occurs when one removes the lower harmonics of a complex tone. In this case the perceived pitch still corresponds closely to the fundamental frequency. However the lowest component must remain (in dependence on the fundamental frequency) in a certain region, otherwise no residue pitch is produced (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 120). A pitch sensation can also be produced for noise with a steep spectral slope. For low- and high-pass noise, the pitch is close to the cut-off frequencies of the filters (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 125). For band-pass noise the pitches correspond to its spectral edges and for narrow-band noise a single pitch at the center frequency is produced (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 128).

A sensation of pitch can be characterized by the adjectives faint or strong. Accordingly, a sound can be arranged on a scale of pitch strength. A pure tone usually produces a perception of pitch with high salience and low ambiguity. The reason is that a pure tone stimulates a very small area of the basilar membrane (Schneider, 2018, p. 607). Pure tones produce the largest pitch strength, whereas complex tones show a pitch strength of at least half the size of a pure tone (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 135). Different types of noises produce a pitch strength, which is usually much smaller than for pure tones, by a factor of 5 to 10 with the exception of narrow-band noise, whose pitch strength is comparable to that of complex tones. Continuous spectra tend to elicit a smaller pitch strength than line spectra with the aforementioned exception of narrow-band noise (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 135). In addition the pitch strength of pure tones increases with its duration up to about 300 ms and with an increasing sound pressure level (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 138). The pitch strength of pure tones is also greatest at mid frequencies in the range of about 750 Hz to 3 kHz (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 139). Furthermore harmonic spectra elicit a more salient perception of pitch than inharmonic spectra (Schneider, 2018, p. 607).

If the frequency is doubled or halved, most subjects report a great similarity between the two pitches. The two tones are perceived as different in their tone height but very similar in their quality (Hesse, 1972, p. 14). This effect is often referred to as octave equivalence. Both acoustic and neurophysiological reasons can be found for this phenomenon (Schneider, 2018, p. 609). If, for example, two sine tones of equal amplitude, a frequency ratio of 2:1 and the same onset are presented simultaneously, they match perfectly, as one period of the lower tone corresponds to two periods of the higher tone. The result is a simple symmetric waveform, where the main period corresponds to the lower tone, which is usually perceived as the fundamental frequency (Schneider, 2018, pp. 609-610). From a neurophysiological point of view,

neuronal activity patterns of individual fibres of the auditory nerve show, that the period between the individual discharges of the neuron corresponds to the period and multiples of the period of the stimulus. Tones at octave intervals therefore show similar neural activity patterns (Schneider, 2018, p. 610). If tones with an octave distance are perceived as very similar in terms of quality, a cycle is produced that repeats itself every octave (Schneider, 2018, p. 611). Such tones have the same chroma and the same name with reference to the chromatic scale in Western music (Gelfand, 2009, p. 222). Thus pitch may be separated in the two components height and tonality or chroma (see Shepard, 1964). Perceiving chroma or tonality is limited to the audible frequency range below about 5000 Hz, whereby the perceived height also increases further for higher frequencies (Gelfand, 2009, p. 223). Interestingly, the neuronal firing of neurons in the cochlear shows phase synchronization for frequencies up to about 4 kHz (Ziemer, 2020, p. 57) to 5 kHz (Gelfand, 2009, p. 223). Temporal coding mechanisms may be important for the perception of chroma (see Gelfand, 2009, p. 223).

1.1.4 Just-noticeable changes in frequency

Fastl and Zwicker (2007) distinguish between two different kinds of sound changes. The first one refers to variation as a function of time and the second to differences between two stimuli, where two successive sounds are presented with a pause in between. Both kinds of sound changes are important for understanding sensations and may be processed differently in our hearing system (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 175). Just-noticeable variations in frequency (JNVF) were examined by Fastl and Zwicker (2007) by using sinusoidal frequency modulation. The human auditory system is most sensitive for modulation frequencies close to 4 Hz (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 183). In Figure 3 the just-noticeable variation in frequency ($2\Delta f$) is illustrated as a function of the carrier frequency, for a modulation frequency of 4 Hz and a level of 60 phon (scale of loudness, see Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 203). At low frequencies (below 500 Hz) the JNVF is almost constant at a value of around 3.6 Hz, whereas above 500 Hz the JNFV increases almost proportionally with about 0.7% of the carrier frequency (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 183).

This shows that our hearing system has a high sensitivity for frequency variations in the medium and high frequency range (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 184). At lower carrier frequencies our hearing system is less sensitive to sinusoidal changes in frequency. At 50 Hz, for example, the JNVF corresponds to a semitone in music (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 183). However, this is probably not true for harmonic musical tones, as they have a spectrum consisting of many partials. Frequency changes of the harmonics with higher frequencies can probably be detected more easily compared to the fundamental frequency (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 183). Just-noticeable frequency modulations are about three times larger in absolute values than just-

Figure 3. Just-noticeable variation in frequency ($2\Delta f$) as a function of the carrier frequency. The modulation frequency is 4 Hz. The dashed line represents an approximation for carrier frequencies above 500 Hz. From Fastl & Zwicker (2007), p. 183.

noticeable frequency differences (JNDs) (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 185). Below 500 Hz, tone bursts can be distinguished with a frequency spacing of 1 Hz, while the JND above 500 Hz increases proportionally with about 0.2% of the frequency (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 186). This data applies to tones with a duration of more than 200 ms. Below the integration time of the auditory system (200 ms) the JND increases with an decreasing test tone duration (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 186).

In reality it is rare to hear sounds in complete silence. Additional noise sources can have an influence on just-noticeable changes. Fastl and Zwicker (2007, p. 192) investigated the influence of partial masking on just-noticeable sound changes at levels above the masked threshold. Therefore the just-noticeable degree of modulation was examined as a function of the test tone level at different background noise levels (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 192). In summary, both the just-noticeable degree of amplitude and the just-noticeable degree of frequency modulation are almost not influenced by a masker at a test tone level of about 20 dB_{SPL} above the masked threshold (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 193). This result also holds true for JNDs of amplitude and frequency. This circumstance ensures that verbal communication is possible even in a noisy environment (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 194).

1.1.5 Critical bands

The strong frequency selectivity of the human hearing system suggests that sound is processed in frequency bands of a relatively narrow width (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 149). The so-called critical band can be defined as “the region affected by the cochlear amplifier” (Ziemer, 2020, p. 71). The cochlear amplifier refers to an “active mechanical response that amplifies low-level and compresses high-level basilar mem-

brane displacements. The amplification is frequency dependent and results in high auditory sensitivity and an extended dynamic range” (Ashmore et al., 2010, p. 1). There is still controversy as to whether the stereocilia or the somatic motility of the outer hair cells are the central mechanism of the cochlear amplifier (Ashmore et al., 2010). Cochlear amplification increases the displacement of the traveling wave in its peak region by up to one hundred times. This is accompanied by a sharpening of the traveling waves envelope at the peak region (see Figure 4) (Ashmore & Kolston, 1994). Fastl and Zwicker (2007) determined the critical bandwidths by using various

Figure 4. Illustration of a traveling wave, propagating along the basilar membrane. Due to the cochlear amplifier the displacement of the traveling wave is increased in its peak region by up to a hundred times. From Ashmore et al. (2010).

methods (see Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 150). By collecting data from more than 50 subjects, Fastl and Zwicker (2007, p. 158) obtained a constant critical bandwidth of about 100 Hz below 500 Hz and an increasing critical bandwidth above 500 Hz by about 20% of the center frequency. The concept of critical bands is important, as the human auditory system processes a broad spectrum in several parts, which correspond to the critical bands (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 158). Moreover, this concept is important to describe several phenomena of the hearing system, like beating and roughness. Fastl and Zwicker (2007) defined a unit called critical-band rate scale. A scale of critical-band rate is obtained, if the critical bands are joined together “in such a way that the upper limit of the lower critical band corresponds to the lower limit of the next higher critical band” (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 158). The audible frequency range can be divided into 25 critical bands. The critical-band rate scale has the unit Bark and ranges from 0 to 24 (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 159). The width of a critical band corresponds to about 1.3 mm on the basilar membrane. Within a distance of 1.3 mm (1 Bark) approximately 150 hair cells can be found, which results in a total of 3600 hair cells along the whole basilar membrane (32 mm and 24 Bark) (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 162). About 27 just-noticeable pitch steps can be differentiated within one critical band (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 162). Con-

trary to what the Bark scale suggests, the “critical bands have no fixed positions, but are areas around a center frequency, [that] are dynamic and adapt to the incoming signal” (Ziemer, 2020, p. 72). Within one critical band, two simultaneously sounding frequencies are processed together and are not perceived as two separate tones. Depending on the distance between the frequencies, a single tone, beating or roughness is perceived (Ziemer, 2020, p. 71). If the frequency difference exceeds the width of the critical band, two separate tones become audible (Ziemer, 2020, p. 71).

1.1.6 Roughness

Amplitude and frequency modulated tones can elicit a sensation of roughness (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 257). A maximum of roughness is achieved at modulation frequencies of around 70 Hz for both amplitude modulated and frequency modulated tones (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 257). To create a sensation of roughness it requires quick changes in amplitude or frequency in a range of 15 to 300 Hz (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 257). Above a modulation frequency of 300 Hz the sensation of roughness vanishes (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 259). The quantitative unit of roughness is called asper, whereas 1 asper refers to the produced roughness of a 1 kHz tone at 60 dB_{SPL}, which is 100% modulated in amplitude with a modulation frequency of 70 Hz (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 257).

Figure 5. Relative roughness as a function of the frequency deviation of a frequency modulated pure tone. The pure tone had a center frequency of 1500 Hz, a level of 70 dB_{SPL} and was modulated with a modulation frequency of 70 Hz. From Fastl & Zwicker (2007), p. 261.

For amplitude as well as frequency modulation roughness shows a dependence on sound pressure. “For an increase in sound pressure level by 40 dB_{SPL} roughness increases by a factor of about 3” (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 260). In general, frequency

modulation can produce much stronger sensations of roughness than amplitude modulation. Roughness close to 6 asper can be achieved with frequency modulation for nearly the entire hearing range (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 261). For frequency modulation roughness also depends strongly on the frequency deviation (Δf , see Figure 5). In Figure 5 a pure tone with a frequency of 1500 Hz and a level of 70 dB_{SPL} was modulated with a modulation frequency of 70 Hz. Above 50 Hz roughness increases almost linearly with the logarithm of Δf , whereas below 50 Hz the sensation of roughness becomes negligible (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 261). The sensation of roughness is closely linked to the critical bands of the basilar membrane. If frequencies fall simultaneously into the same critical band, they are perceived as a single sound, with the interval between frequencies determining the sensation of a single tone, roughness or beats (Ziemer, 2020, p.71). With two sine tones of the same amplitude, one with a constant frequency and one with a continuously rising frequency, the sound changes with increasing distance from a single tone to a slow modulation to an increasing roughness and an area where strong beats occur (Schneider, 2018, p. 632). If the distance is further increased, roughness decreases again (Schneider, 2018, p. 632) and finally two separate tones can be heard if the frequency spacing is greater than the corresponding critical bandwidth (Ziemer, 2020, p. 71).

1.1.7 Sharpness and sensory pleasantness

The sensation of sharpness depends largely on the spectral envelope of a sound, whereas the fine structure of the spectrum is of less importance. The sharpness for noise with a continuous spectrum is the same as the sharpness of a sound with a line spectrum, “if the spectral envelopes measured in critical-band levels are the same” (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 239). The dependence on level is relatively small, as well as the dependence on bandwidth, “as long as the bandwidth is smaller than a critical band” (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 239). For narrow band sounds the center frequency and the spectral content are most important for the sensation of sharpness (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 239). With increasing center frequency the sharpness increases proportionally to the critical band rate up to 3 kHz, whereas above 3 kHz sharpness increases faster. This way the sensation of high frequency sounds is essentially determined by their sharpness (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 240). Another important factor is the bandwidth. If, for example, additional noise at high frequencies is added to a narrow-band noise, the sharpness increases. The opposite effect can be observed, when the lower cut-off frequency is moved towards lower frequencies. Thus sharpness can be reduced by adding lower frequency sound (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 241).

“Sensory pleasantness is a more complex sensation that is influenced by elementary auditory sensations such as roughness, sharpness, tonality, and loudness” (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 243). The influence of sharpness and roughness on sensory

pleasantness was investigated by Fastl and Zwicker (2007, p. 243) using pure tones, narrow-band noise (30 Hz bandwidth) and band-pass noise (1 kHz bandwidth). The "sensory pleasantness decreases with increasing sharpness" (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 243). The highest sensory pleasantness is found in pure tones and the lowest in band-pass noise (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 243). Similarly, the sensory pleasantness decreases with increasing roughness, although to a lesser extent. Furthermore, the sensory pleasantness increases with increasing tonality, whereas tonality is "a feature distinguishing noise versus tone quality of sounds" (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 244). Overall, sharpness has the greatest influence on sensory pleasantness. Roughness and tonality show a similar influence on sensory pleasantness, although to a lesser extent (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 245). However, besides physical parameters, the perceived pleasantness also depends on the listener's subjective relationship to the sound (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 245).

1.1.8 Masking

Masking is a phenomenon, which can be experienced in many everyday situations. For example, in a piece of music instruments can mask each other, if one instrument is much louder than another one (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 61). If the loud instrument pauses, one can hear the soft instrument. This is an example of simultaneous masking. The sound pressure level of the soft instrument necessary to be just audible in the presence of the loud instrument is called masked threshold. Using the terminology of psychoacoustics, the soft instrument is the test tone and the loud instrument the masker (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 61). In almost all cases the masked threshold lies above the threshold in quiet. They become identical in case of huge frequency differences between test tone and masker (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 61). In general one can distinguish between monaural and binaural masking (Ziemer, 2020, p. 74). In a monaural masking paradigm the masker and the test tone are heard on the same ear (Ziemer, 2020, p. 73), whereas in a binaural masking (or central masking) paradigm masker and the test tone are presented to opposing ears (Ziemer, 2020, p. 79). Below, the basic principles of masking are discussed using results of a monaural masking paradigm.

Simultaneous masking refers to a masking phenomenon in the case of simultaneous sounds (Ziemer, 2020, p. 74). A traveling wave, which moves along the basilar membrane, has its peak in a specific frequency dependent area. Only if a traveling wave can protrude from the envelope of other simultaneous traveling waves it is further processed through cochlear amplification, otherwise it is masked (Ziemer, 2020, p. 74). Simultaneous sounds therefore increase the absolute threshold of a sound to a masking threshold. In order to become audible, the sound needs to cross this masking threshold (Ziemer, 2020, p. 74). In Figure 6 the masking threshold of a test tone masked by a 1 kHz tone of different sound pressure levels is depicted

as a function of the test tone frequency. Figure 6 clearly shows that the masking area of a tonal masker depends on its intensity and its frequency. The masked threshold is greatest in the immediate vicinity of the masker's frequency. With increasing distance from this frequency, the masked threshold decreases. In addition, the overall masked threshold and the masking range increases with the intensity of the masker. Both phenomena are plausible due to the characteristics of the basilar membrane. The largest deflection of the basilar membrane can be found within the frequency range of the masker. Furthermore, the deflection of the basilar membrane depends on the intensity of the masker. As the intensity increases, the deflection increases and affects a larger area of the basilar membrane. For high frequencies of the test tone, the slope becomes less steep with an increasing level of the masker, leading to a greater spread of masking towards higher frequencies (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, pp. 68-69). The reason for the broader masking area towards high frequencies lies in the characteristics of the basilar membrane. At the oval window the sound waves enter the cochlear and induce traveling waves, which reach their peak in a certain region and collapse quickly behind it (Ziemer, 2020, p. 74). As the peak of low frequencies lie at the apex and for high frequencies at the base of the basilar membrane, traveling waves of low frequencies also excite the region of high frequencies but not the other way around (Ziemer, 2020, p. 74). As traveling waves collapse quickly behind their peak region, masking towards frequencies below the frequency of the tonal masker is relatively small (see Figure 6). A greater spread of masking towards lower frequencies for low sound pressure levels (<40 dB_{SPL}) of the masker might be explained by the occurrence of difference tones. These nonlinear components do get produced internally, where the physical stimulus is changed into an internal stimulus (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 74). Due to difference tones this internal stimulus is broader and this way more masking is produced towards low frequencies. Towards high frequencies this effect is probably of little importance, since masking is already much more pronounced in this direction (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 74).

In nature one rarely encounters pure tones. For example, the sound of most instruments is composed of a fundamental frequency and further harmonics (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 71). The masking patterns of instruments depend on their individual spectra. In contrast to other instruments, a flute for instance, has only a narrow masking range, since its spectrum comes close to a pure tone (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 71). In Figure 7 the masking thresholds of pure test tones masked by complex tones of different levels (40 and 60 dB_{SPL}) are depicted as a function of the test tone frequency. The complex tones are composed of a fundamental frequency of 200 Hz and nine further harmonics, all with identical sound pressure levels and random phase. The partials are reflected in the peaks of the masking threshold curve, which approaches threshold in quiet about one to two octaves above the last harmonic of

Figure 6. The relationship between the masked threshold of a test tone and its frequency for various levels of a 1 kHz tone. The dashed line indicates the absolute hearing threshold. From Fastl and Zwicker (2007), p. 68.

Figure 7. The relationship between the masked threshold of a test tone and its frequency for two levels of a complex tone, consisting of the fundamental frequency at 200 Hz and nine additional harmonics. The dashed line indicates the absolute hearing threshold. From Fastl and Zwicker (2007), p. 71.

the complex tone (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 71). In addition, music and speech are strongly influenced by the temporal structure of sounds, as a constant change between loud and quiet sounds can be observed (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 78). Consonants for example, which are relatively faint, are often masked by vowels, which are the loudest phones in English (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 78). These effects are investigated by using maskers of a limited time span together with short test tone bursts. For further details on temporal effects of masking see Fastl (1976, 1979), Fastl and Zwicker (2007) or Oxenham and Moore (1994).

1.1.9 Auditory scene analysis

The fundamental problem of auditory scene analysis is the construction of separate mental descriptions of the different sound-generating events in the environment, despite the fact that the acoustic signal reaching our ears is a mixture of the effects

of different acoustic events (Bregman, 1990, p. 641). Each perceived feature of an auditory input is computed from a subset of that input. Such a feature is supposed to be meaningful in that it describes a quality of a sound that was produced by a particular event in the environment (Bregman, 1990, p. 661). In auditory scene analysis a single event is represented by a perceptual unit that Bregman (1990, p. 10) refers to as auditory stream; it can be seen as the counterpart of an object in vision (Bregman, 1990, p. 11). A stream is an entity to which we can assign various properties of the auditory input, whereas each property is usually assigned to only one stream at any given time (this is called the principle of exclusive allocation, see Bregman, 1990, p. 12). According to Bregman (1990, p. 641) the auditory system solves the problem of grouping the auditory input into streams by two different processes, namely primitive processes of auditory grouping and the use of schema, that provide knowledge about familiar sounds and guide the listening process. This chapter is based on Bregman's book *Auditory scene analysis* from 1990 (pp. 641-705).

1.1.9.1 Primitive auditory scene analysis

Primitive auditory scene analysis seems to perform a large number of separate analyses of the incoming acoustic signal, both for a specific time and for a specific frequency region. The individual regions are analyzed in terms of their intensity, the pattern of fluctuations, the direction of frequency changes and their spatial position. The challenge of the auditory scene analysis is then to group these regions so that each group can be assigned to a specific event in the environment. Such groups must be formed both across time and across the spectrum, what Bregman calls sequential and simultaneous integration respectively. Both forms of segregation or integration are based on primitive grouping principles (e.g. timbre, proximity, common fate, continuity), which will be explained below. Primitive scene analysis shares several aspects with the Gestalt theory of grouping. "It sees the effects of similarity, temporal proximity and continuity as innate principles that determine grouping" (Bregman, 1990, p. 654), also including the idea of competitiveness between different grouping principles.

1.1.9.2 Sequential integration

There are several factors that affect the grouping of a sequence of acoustic signals. "These include their fundamental frequency, their temporal proximity, the shape of their spectra, their intensity, and their apparent spatial origin" (Bregman, 1990, p. 649). In the following, grouping principles of sequential integration are discussed.

Temporal proximity

Auditory stream segregation can already be found in baroque music, where a sin-

gle instrument can give the impression of two melody lines by quickly alternating between a higher and a lower melody line. Therefore stream segregation can occur, when tones in a sequence quickly jump back and forth between two frequency regions. If the speed of the tones and the frequency spacing between the two regions are sufficiently high, the listener perceives two streams of tones, one in the upper frequency region and another in the lower frequency region. This way the listener gets the impression that there are two different sound sources. The most important factors influencing auditory stream segregation are the speed at which the tones are played and the frequency difference between the two frequency regions. With an increasing speed of the tone rate and an increasing frequency spacing between adjacent tones, the segregation becomes easier for the listener. However, the extent to which stream segregation is achieved depends largely on the listener's attention, which can be directed either to all tones of the sequence or only to the tones of one of the frequency regions (see chapter 1.1.9.4 for schema-based segregation). Here segregation seems to be analogous to a Gestalt principle, in which grouping takes place via proximity. The high notes of a sequence are more likely to be grouped together, if they are placed close together in time, whereas this can be achieved by speeding up the sequence.

Spatial Location

The primitive scene analysis tends to group sounds that originate at the same position in space rather than those that originate at different positions in space. Spatially based stream segregation is most effective when the sounds further differ from each other in other features.

Timbre

An additional factor that influences the similarity of tones and thus the grouping into streams is timbre. For example, timbre plays a role for the sequential perception of music. "Timbre changes are rarely large enough and rapid enough to cause the line of melody to split into parallel streams" (Bregman, 1990, p. 677). Nonetheless, for small changes in pitch and large changes of timbre it is possible to induce stream segregation. Timbre is often used to ensure that certain musical phrases are perceived as a unit. Rapid changes in timbre indicate the occurrence of a new event. If, instead, timbre changes continuously, it is more likely that a single changing event is present. The question of what dimensions underlie timbre is one that has been approached in various ways. One approach attempts to determine the underlying dimensions of timbre by using similarity ratings from test persons regarding different sound pairs. One of these dimensions is the brightness of sounds (see e.g. Iverson & Krumhansel, 1993). Tones with a similar brightness are more likely to be assigned to the same stream. Note, that the perception of timbre is already the result of spectral integration, as it refers to a perceived quality of a grouping of the auditory input.

Continuity

The continuity of an acoustic signal influences stream segregation. Tones that alternate between different frequency ranges can be connected to each other via a frequency glide, thus making it easier to group them into a single stream. Thus acoustic continuity is an indication that a sound sequence originates from a single event in the environment.

Further factors of sequential grouping

For complex tones, the grouping of sounds is influenced by both the fundamental frequency and the average frequency of their spectrum (i.e. the impression of brightness) in an additive way. Thus a pure tone and a complex tone with the same pitch can be assigned to different streams due to differences in the perceived brightness. The spectrum of two successive harmonic tones is probably compared by the auditory scene analysis in terms of two different properties. On the one hand, the same intensity pattern of the harmonics of two tones may indicate a common resonator. On the other hand, tones can be perceived as similar if the peaks in the spectra occur at overtones with the same order. If the sound is more continuous, i.e. it cannot be divided into discrete tones, the auditory system can still form units. This is achieved via discontinuities in the sound, in particular when there is a sudden increase in intensity. Units formed in this way can then be further grouped into streams based on similarities. The same factors as discussed above influence sequential groupings when sounds are mixed together, whereas in this case only parts of the overall sound are grouped sequentially. In addition, the factors that influence the sequential grouping of sounds can both reinforce and compete with each other (this also applies for spectral grouping). For example, a particular feature may prefer a grouping between stimuli A and B and X and Y, but another feature may prefer a grouping between stimuli A and X and B and Y. The degree of similarity with regard to the relevant features and the importance of the respective dimensions determine which elements are grouped together. This way a certain sound can be taken out of its current stream by making a change with regard to a certain dimension.

Ich würde erst über spectral und dann über temporal integration sprechen, denn zB timbre entsteht vor allem durch spektrale integration und bildet dann eine der Grundlagen für zeitliche Integration

1.1.9.3 Spectral integration

In the case of a sound mixture, the auditory system must decide which of the components that are currently being received should be assigned to a specific event in the environment. If two pure tones have a common start and end point, the listener tends to perceive them as components of a single complex tone. However, as the frequency spacing between two components increases, they are more likely to be assigned to different streams. Also, partials with high intensity are more easily segregated from the rest of the spectrum. Sequential grouping and spectral grouping

seem to compete with each other. If the two tones (say A and B) were alternated with an additional tone (C), that was close in frequency to one of the two tones (here tone A), tone A tends to be interpreted as a repetition of tone C. Tone A can either be assigned to a sequential stream with tone C or fuse with tone B into a complex tone. To group certain frequency components, the auditory system searches for correlations between parts of the spectrum that are unlikely to occur by chance. For example, a complex spectrum may contain a simpler one from a previous sound (see above). The auditory system would then interpret this part of the spectrum as a continuation of the previous sound and the rest of the spectrum as a new sound ("old-plus-new" heuristic). In the following, further grouping principles of spectral integration are discussed.

Harmonicity

The auditory system preferentially groups partials that can be assigned as harmonics to a common fundamental frequency. One can immediately see the function of this kind of grouping, as a variety of natural sounds, including animal sounds or the human voice, have a harmonic spectrum. If all partials can be assigned to a certain number of fundamental frequencies, it is likely that a corresponding number of sounds will be perceived. Due to this way of grouping, a separate pitch and timbre can be perceived for each group of partials. Such a grouping also has the effect that partials in a particular group fuse into an overall impression, so that the individual partials are not audible. Also, harmonic complex tones that are one octave apart fuse strongly, because the partials of the higher tone correspond to even harmonics of the lower tone.

Common fate

The Gestalt principle of common fate states that separate parts of the visual field are grouped together if they change simultaneously in the same way (e.g. move in the same direction at the same time). In auditory perception, this principle refers to correlations between partials with respect to changes in their frequency or amplitude. Two forms of frequency changes are likely to be important in this context. On the one hand there are micromodulations, e.g. tiny changes in the pitch of the human voice that occur at any given time, and on the other hand there is a slower form of frequency modulation that occurs, for example, when the pitch of the voice is changed voluntarily. It appears that a synchronization of the partials with respect to one or both forms of frequency modulation causes the auditory system to interpret them as parts of a single sound. Similarly, the auditory system tends to group parts of the spectrum, that change synchronously in their amplitude. Here the synchrony of the amplitude changes of different sounds plays an important role. There are strong changes in amplitude at the beginning and at the end of a sound. The components of a single sound tend to begin and end at the same time. A synchronous onset and offset can therefore serve as a cue to group auditory material.

Spatial location

The spectral components that come from the same direction in space are more likely to be grouped together than those that come from different directions. To perform such a grouping, the auditory system has to make an independent estimate of the spatial origin for each distinguishable frequency band of the spectrum. For example, the perceived position of a particular frequency band of noise can be specified by the relative delay of that frequency band in one ear compared to the other ear. Although spatial evidence is an important cue for auditory scene analysis, it is only one of several, as most people can separate sounds that occur simultaneously, even with a monaural recording. In general, the localization of sounds via auditory scene analysis is based on the assumptions, “that sound-producing events tend to persist over time, to move only slowly in space, and to give rise to sounds that have a coherent inner structure” (Bregman, 1990, p. 660).

Fusion and masking

When different components of the auditory input are grouped together, they fuse, so that the individual components become inaudible. In a similar way, in the case of masking, the audibility of acoustic signals is reduced when other acoustic signals are present. In the case of a masked sound, it is not possible to tell whether or not it is present in a sound mixture. On the other side a sound fuses with other sounds, when it can no longer be distinguished from the others as a separate sound. However, a change in the overall sound quality might be noticed, when this sound is added or removed. Many factors that influence the fusion of sounds also play an important role in masking. A sound is masked less easily when it is micromodulated in frequency or amplitude. Moreover, a sound is less easily masked if the masker does not start at the same time or originates from a different spatial position. In the case of frequency bands, masking can be reduced by grouping the masker with a frequency band that is far away from the target sound. These similarities suggest a common physiological mechanism of fusion and masking.

1.1.9.4 Schema-based auditory scene analysis

Primitive processes “are assumed to establish basic groupings among parts of the sensory evidence so that the number and the qualities of the sounds that are ultimately perceived will be based on these groupings” (Bregman, 1990, p. 665). However, the auditory perception of the listener is additionally structured by knowledge of certain types of acoustic signals. For example, these include speech, machine sounds and music. Knowledge about these sounds is stored in so-called schemas, which contain information about certain regularities of different size and duration. There could be a scheme for a piano tone, another for a musical phrase and one for a major triad. Schemas are activated when a corresponding pattern is detected in

the auditory input, which is then grouped so that the underlying construct of the schema can be perceived. For example, a schema-based grouping of auditory input can be observed when two vowels sound simultaneously with the same fundamental frequency and identical spatial position. It would not be possible to hear the two vowels separately on the basis of the primitive grouping processes that have been described here. However, it is often possible to hear two vowels. In contrast to primitive segregation, which does not require learning or voluntary attention, schemas are likely to be developed over the course of life for certain sound classes and are controlled by attentional processes. Once attention is needed to perform a particular task, schemas play a role, e.g. if one is waiting to hear one's own name in a list. There is further evidence that a distinction between a primitive and a schema-based scene analysis is reasonable. According to Bregman (1990), there are studies showing that already infants use some of the principles of primitive scene analysis, whereby infants probably have no corresponding schemas for the stimuli used in these studies. Furthermore, in a sequence of alternating high and low tones, the effects of the distance between the frequency regions and the speed of the sequence on grouping processes depend on what the listener is concentrating on. Only a small distance between the two frequency regions is required when attention is focused on only one of the streams and increasing the frequency spacing or changing the speed of the sequence does not seem to facilitate segregation or change it in any way. On the other hand it is difficult for the listener to follow the whole sequence, if the primitive segregation is strong. Therefore, using an attention-based process, it seems easier to subdivide a sequence into separate streams than to integrate it into a single stream. Bregman (1990) consequently suggests that both primitive segregation, which is influenced by tone rate and frequency spacing, and schema-based segregation, which allows focusing on one of the streams by controlling attention, are present. In summary, various experiments and observations show that "separate pitches, timbres (e.g. perceived roughness), vowel identification, and even locations can be computed separately on the streams created by scene analysis" (Bregman, 1990, p. 662). Otherwise, the whole auditory input would contribute to an overall sound and only one sound would be perceived at any given moment.

1.1.9.5 Practical application

Knowledge about principles of auditory scene analysis offers numerous possibilities for practical applications. They are useful for the automatic recognition of sounds, including speech, or the automatic transcription of music. Another area of application is the sound design of signals in certain working environments. It is important for a safe and smooth workflow that auditory signals, such as instructions or warnings, can be separated by the listener. For example, a warning signal should not be grouped with other signals, as this changes the perceived sound quality and the

warning signal may not be recognized by the listener. Furthermore, the weighting of certain sequential, spectral or spatial cues for the grouping of sound is likely to be different for each person. An individual profile of a listener may help to predict problems in certain situations.

1.2 Sonification

In this chapter, the concept of sonification is introduced. The following sections first define and differentiate the concepts of sonification and auditory display. This is followed by a discussion of how sonifications can be used for a monitoring task, which is particularly relevant in the context of the present study. Several issues that need to be considered for the design of a sonification in general and in particular for the design of a parameter mapping sonification are addressed. Finally the role of aesthetics in the field of sonification is discussed.

1.2.1 Sonification and auditory display

The purpose of an auditory display is to help the listener to better understand the structure of the data the display is based on (Hermann et al., 2011). It comprises all aspects of an interaction system between human and machine. This includes the setup of the auditory display, forms of interaction with the system and the technical realization of converting data to sound (Hermann et al., 2011). Sonification represents the core element of an auditory display. It is “the technique of rendering sound in response to data and interactions” (Hermann et al., 2011, p. 1), with the focus on conveying information to the listener (Hermann et al., 2011). It takes human auditory perceptual abilities into account, so that the relationships in the data become accessible to the listener (Walker & Nees, 2011).

Sonification can also be defined as a “subtype of auditory displays that use non-speech audio to represent information” (Walker & Nees, 2011, p. 9). Although sonification can clearly be considered a subset of auditory displays, it is often not clear how the two concepts can be differentiated from each other (Walker & Nees, 2011). To avoid possible confusion, mainly the term sonification will be used in the present study, as this represents the core element of an auditory display anyway. Hermann (2008) defines sonification as follows: “A technique that uses data as input, and generates sound signals . . . may be called sonification, if and only if” the translation is objective (based on objective relations in the data), systematic, reproducible and can also be used for different data (p. 2). A different definition was proposed by Kramer et al. (1999): “Sonification is the transformation of data relations into perceived relations in an acoustic signal for the purposes of facilitating communication or interpretation” (p. 3). This definition puts a stronger focus on the purpose of sonification, which is to provide the listener with information about

the data in an accessible way.

1.2.2 Sonification in a monitoring function

Besides visual perception, auditory perception is also suitable for processing information (Kramer et al., 1999). In certain forms of information processing, the auditory system may even be superior to the visual system. The communication of information via a sonification is particularly appropriate for environments in which several variables or temporally complex information need to be monitored (Kramer et al., 1999). Process monitoring deals with “one or more series of temporally-related data” (Vickers, 2011, p. 455). As sound is a temporal medium, process monitoring seems to be an application, which is particularly suitable for sonifications (Vickers, 2011).

The human auditory system is very sensitive to temporal properties, or to changes of sounds over time as well as to the periodicity of a continuous signal (Kramer et al., 1999). Data that changes or disappears quickly can be easily overlooked on a visual display, whereas a sonification makes it easy to recognize (Kramer et al., 1999). In contrast to visual perception, auditory perception does not require an orientation in a certain direction (Kramer et al., 1999). Therefore, sonifications can also be used in situations where the user is already busy with an additional visual task (Kramer et al., 1999). Moreover, hearing is obligatory, as one can not prevent sound from reaching the ear (Sanderson, Liu, & Jenkins, 2009). Sonifications are thus particularly suitable for monitoring and alerting functions. In a monitoring situation, the listener has to pay attention to the sonification over a certain period of time, identify relevant sound events and be able to react to them appropriately (Walker & Nees, 2011). Such sound events usually occur when certain thresholds are exceeded, as for instance an alarm tone sounding at a critical level of oxygen saturation (Walker & Nees, 2011). Walker and Nees (2011) further distinguish between monitoring- and awareness-related tasks. Awareness-related tasks are not so much about conveying critical thresholds, but rather about providing a continuous feedback on certain processes. This avoids the issue of when information is communicated to the listener (Sanderson et al., 2009).

This applies to pulse oximetry, as the listener has to be continuously aware of changes in oxygen saturation and heart rate. The sonification of a pulse oximeter provides information about normal states, so that the listener is confirmed in the patient’s momentary condition and putting her/him into a sudden state of alert is avoided (Sanderson et al., 2009). According to a review on different displays used for monitoring in anesthesia by Sanderson, Watson, and Russell (2005) continuous sonifications in pulse oximetry can shorten reaction times and improve the ability to perform additional tasks simultaneously. In summary, a sonification is an ideal choice for monitoring tasks. This includes pulse oximetry in particular, where the

use of sonifications is already well established.

1.2.3 Designing a sonification

In the following, different issues are discussed, that need to be considered when designing a sonification. Often decisions concerning the design are based on intuition, convenience or the possibilities to manipulate the sound parameters. A greater focus should be placed on the perception of auditory signals (Bliss & Spain, 2007). Hence it is important to develop guidelines for the design of sonifications. These should be based on research in psychoacoustics, perceptual psychology and cognitive sciences (Kramer et al., 1999). The field of psychoacoustics and the knowledge about how the hearing system processes acoustic stimuli and extracts information from sound offer a valuable foundation for design choices (Carlile, 2011). By considering psychoacoustic principles, sonifications that are intuitively understood by the listeners can be designed (see e.g. Ziemer, Black, & Schultheis, 2017). Also Ferguson, Cabrera, Beilharz, and Song (2006) argue for the consideration of psychoacoustics in the design of sonifications. According to Ferguson et al. (2006) the application of psychoacoustic models allows the development of an auditory display that is "easy to interpret and pleasant to listen to" (p. 113). The most commonly used models describe the psychoacoustic sensations of loudness, sharpness, roughness and fluctuation strength, which are evoked by all sounds by a certain degree (Ferguson et al., 2006). When using an acoustic parameter like frequency, other sensations like sharpness or loudness are implicitly present (Ferguson et al., 2006). The simple mapping of orthogonal input parameters to individual acoustic parameters can therefore lead to problems with the interpretation of the auditory display. For example, a change in frequency can affect the perceived pitch, loudness and brightness (Ziemer et al., 2017). To avoid possible confusion in the case of orthogonal input variables, an orthogonal relationship should also be attempted between the psychoacoustic variables. When one psychoacoustic variable changes, others should be perceived as constant. Apart from psychoacoustics further factors need to be considered to design an effective sonification.

It has to be decided what information should be conveyed via the sonification and whether a visual or auditory display is advantageous (Sanderson et al., 2009). The issue of when to display data is of particular importance for auditory alarms, but might be of little concern in a monitoring task, as the sonification continuously conveys relevant information to the listener (Sanderson et al., 2009). It must also be considered who will hear the sonification (Sanderson et al., 2009). "Individual differences in perceptual, cognitive and musical abilities" are important predictors for the successful communication of information via the sonification (Walker & Nees, 2011, p. 27). Advantages and disadvantages of common forms of auditory displays, including auditory icons, earcons, spearcons, parameter mapping or model-based

sonifications should be considered. Auditory icons were defined by Gaver (1997) as "everyday sounds mapped to computer events by analogy with everyday sound-producing events" (p. 18). For example, the icon of a file can be linked to a sound that is generated, when one clicks on a mousepad. In contrast to auditory icons, earcons use music-like sounds to represent the data, resulting in a more abstract relationship (McGookin & Brewster, 2004). Spearcons are generated by speeding up the audio recording of speech without changing the pitch until the speech is no longer recognizable (Walker et al., 2013). Model-based sonifications put their focus on interactions with the user of the sonification. They provide a framework for translating the user's actions into acoustic responses. Such sonifications typically remain silent without any external stimulation (Hermann et al., 2011). Parameter mapping sonifications are described in more detail in the following section. After implementation, an empirical evaluation of the sonification should be conducted to guarantee a certain performance standard. In view of the potential users, a representative sample should be chosen for the evaluation study (Sanderson et al., 2009). Also factors that might influence the performance with the sonification should be considered for the sampling process and analyzed in regard to their influence on performance. Sonifications that systematically differ in their mapping strategies, or more generally in their use of different forms of auditory feedback, should be compared in their effectiveness with respect to a particular task (Hohagen & Wöllner, 2019). Moreover, most people have little experience in dealing with sonifications as it is not a part of standard education (Walker & Nees, 2011). Therefore the design should be made as simple and intuitive as possible, if the listener has little opportunities to practice. Finally, masking by other sound sources should be avoided, while additional noise should be kept to a minimum (Sanderson et al., 2009).

1.2.4 Parameter mapping sonification

With parameter mapping sonifications, a continuous stream of data is mapped to a parameter of the sound generation, so that a change in the data leads to a change in the sound, e.g. by changing the frequency of a tone (Henkelmann, 2007). The sonification of conventional pulse oximeters is a form of a parameter mapping sonification (see chapter 1.2.6). Sanderson et al. (2009) distinguish between different mapping principles. Semantic mapping refers to specifying the number of different auditory streams, selecting the acoustic dimensions that should convey information, and considering how relationships in the data can be conveyed by changes in the acoustic dimensions (Sanderson et al., 2009). When several simultaneous data streams are involved, findings on auditory scene analysis provide an important basis for the sound design (Walker & Nees, 2011). Moreover, it is important to choose an optimal polarity and scaling for the translation of the data into sound. In an experiment by Walker (2002), participants estimated the magnitude of different

stimuli, such as temperature, pressure, speed or dollars via the sound dimensions pitch and tempo. The results showed, that both the preferred polarity and scaling depended on the underlying data type. For instance, 14 of 16 participants preferred a positive polarity between speed and frequency, i.e. an increase in frequency was accompanied by an increase in speed, whereas only 6 of 16 participants preferred a positive polarity between dollars and frequency. Taking the preferred polarity in a sonification into account probably leads to less confusion and a higher effectiveness of the chosen mapping (Walker, 2002). Similarly Ferguson et al. (2006) suggest, that certain psychoacoustic parameters could reflect the character of certain data types particularly well. Depending on the psychoacoustic parameter, the preferred polarity and scaling for a given data type may change.

Scaling decisions should also depend on how accurately certain information is supposed to be communicated to the listener. Psychoacoustic considerations should be included, as a change in the data can only be communicated, if the human auditory system is able to detect the corresponding change in sound. In addition, contextual cues can help to identify exact values, analogous to the x and y axes of a visual graph. For instance, it is difficult to estimate an exact value via pitch without a reference point, as this would require the listener to have absolute pitch (Walker & Nees, 2011). Sanderson et al. (2009) point out the importance of attentional and urgency mapping. In case of pulse oximetry, the anaesthetist's attention should be reliably directed to the sonification, when certain sound changes occur, whereas her/his attention should not be distracted from other tasks or disturbed by the sonification (Sanderson et al., 2009). Finally the relative urgency of a situation might be conveyed by certain sound properties of alarms (Sanderson et al., 2009).

1.2.5 Aesthetics

“Aesthetics is commonly defined as the study of beauty” (Huron, 2016, p. 233). The term aesthetics is therefore often associated with music or art. However, aesthetics should not be confused with art. Essentially, aesthetics refers to a “sensuous perception” (Barass & Vickers, 2011, p. 158). Following this meaning we make aesthetic judgements every day about various objects (Barass & Vickers, 2011). According to Barass and Vickers (2011), sonifications are distinguished from other tonal practices by the underlying functional intention. And further: “The defining feature of sonification is a pragmatic information aesthetic that combines the functionality of information design with the aesthetic sensibilities of the sonic arts” (Barass & Vickers, 2011, p. 152). However, so far mainly the functionality of sonifications was explored by scientists, engineers and technologists. The sonifications used in these experiments were often criticized as unpleasant to listen to by the participants (Barass & Vickers, 2011). The remaining chapter is mainly based on Barass and Vickers (2011).

Henkelmann (2007) proposes different methods for the sonification of realtime motion data. In particular, Henkelmann (2007) discusses alternatives for pitch-based sonifications. Aesthetic judgement of sound is influenced by pitch to a greater extent than by other sound parameters, especially in the case of intervals and several streams of varying pitch (Henkelmann, 2007). To make pitch-based sonification more pleasant to listen to, dissonant intervals, very high pitches, high pitch strength and matching of more than one independent pitch streams should be avoided (Henkelmann, 2007). Moreover, according to Hekelmann (2007), a discrete pitch mapping is more pleasant to listen to than a continuous change in pitch. Also Barrass, Schaffert, and Barrass (2010) examined the aesthetics of different sonification techniques. Six different interactive sonifications were created for the use in outdoor sports. The participants were not given a specific task, allowing the sonifications to be used for various activities such as running, jogging, yoga etc. Results show that the so-called *algorithmic music* (a mixture of three FM synthesis instruments) was most preferred by the participants, followed by the *sinification* (parameter mapping between acceleration data and the pitch of a sine tone) and the *musification* (algorithmic music with a higher complexity). At the same time, some participants showed the least preference for the sinification and the musification. Barass et al. (2010) conclude "that there are subgroups with different aesthetic and functional requirements" (p. 28). These subgroups are possibly based on differences in competitiveness, previous experience with sonifications or the specific sport (Barass et al., 2010). A possible interaction between functional and aesthetic aspects of sonifications was also examined by Leplâtre and McGregor (2004). An auditory email preview was created, that informed the listener about incoming messages. Three groups of 12 participants were asked to evaluate different sounds of the email preview, whereas each group had to perform an additional task of varying difficulty. The results show, that the difficulty of the performed task had an influence on both the functional and the aesthetic evaluation of the sonification. Therefore, if a sound is evaluated poorly regarding its functionality due to the difficulty of a task, this could lead to a poor aesthetic evaluation (Leplâtre & McGregor, 2004). This provides further evidence, that the perceived aesthetics of a sonification depends on the interaction context and the specific task. Walker and Nees (2011) further suggest a causal relationship, where the consideration of aesthetic aspects facilitates the interpretation of a sonification.

The question remains, how aesthetic aspects can be integrated into the process of designing a sonification. Is it possible to provide a set of aesthetic guidelines for the design of a sonification? According to Barass and Vickers (2011), it is not possible to say whether aesthetic guidelines are desirable or possible at all. One of the main problems is the diversity of disciplines and techniques in the field of sonifications. Each type of application could have its own set of aesthetic guidelines. Moreover,

ideas about what constitutes an aesthetic sound are highly individual and it is not possible to design one universal aesthetic experience (Barass & Vickers, 2011). Another approach could consider psychoacoustic principles. Fastl and Zwicker (2007, p. 245) offer a model for sensory pleasantness, which can provide a basis for the design of pleasant sounds. However, when designing sonifications, the field of aesthetics is not equal to finding pleasant sounds. According to Vickers, Hogg, and Worrall (2017) a sonification does not have to be perceived as pleasant. The sonification must rather be suitable for the task in question, as pleasantness, for example in the case of warning signals, can prevent the communication of important information (Vickers et al., 2017). Taking aesthetic aspects into account when designing sonifications essentially refers to the task of making the underlying data sound in a way, that is intuitively comprehensible to the listener and does not appear arbitrary (Vickers et al., 2017). "An imposed sound, that is closer to the nature and context of the data – through attention to its aesthetic qualities- may lead to a quicker and more intuitive understanding of the phenomenon being sonified" (Vickers et al., 2017, p. 100). And further:

For sonification, the aesthetic is about trying to cultivate 'right' listening without the illusion that the sounds of a sonification are somehow an inevitable or unmediated result of the underlying data. The aesthetic enters at the point of constructing the subject-position such that a hearing-in becomes more probable, that is, something in the aesthetic of the sound has to match the phenomenon being revealed. (Vickers, et al., 2017, p. 105)

1.2.6 Sonification and pulse oximetry

1.2.6.1 Pulse oximetry and SpO₂ in premature infants

Via pulse oximetry oxygen saturation (SpO₂) and heart rate can be measured (Dawson & Morley, 2010). "Pulse oximetry is based on the red and infrared light absorption characteristics of oxygenated and deoxygenated haemoglobin" (Dawson & Morley, 2010, p. 204). This method determines SpO₂ by the amount of light transmitted through a pulsatile tissue bed, whereas the sensor can be placed around a hand or foot. More precisely, light with two different wavelengths (red and infrared light) is emitted via a diode and captured on the other side by a photoreceptor (Dawson & Morley, 2010). Since the arterial blood volume increases with every heartbeat and thus more light is absorbed during this period, it is also possible to determine the heart rate via the resulting peaks (Dawson & Morley, 2010).

In acute medical care, oxygen treatment has been used for a variety of pathological states (Sjöberg & Singer, 2013). This was justified with the aim of avoiding hypoxemia and tissue hypoxia. However, studies have shown that hyperoxia has vasoconstrictor effects, reducing blood flow in the affected tissue (Sjöberg & Singer, 2013). In addition, oxygen can, besides positive effects, also have toxic effects,

such as induced mucosal inflammation, pneumonitis or retinopathy of prematurity (Sjöberg & Singer, 2013). In the recent past, supplemental oxygen has therefore not been used in various acute medical care settings, as for example during resuscitation of asphyxiated newborns (Sjöberg & Singer, 2013). Habre and Peták (2014) point out age-related factors of hyperoxia with regard to the preoperative use of oxygen. For both very young and very old patients, the risks of hyperoxia are much greater than the benefits. In premature and newborn children, oxidative stress can be a major threat to the developing lungs and the brain (Habre & Peták, 2014). The negative effects of oxidative stress on premature babies are also emphasized by Saugstad (2005).

Given the results of the studies described above, it is important, especially for preterm infants, to determine an SpO₂ range that minimizes negative effects of both very high and very low SpO₂ levels. In a meta-analysis by Saugstad and Aune (2013), optimal oxygenation of infants with an extremely low birth weight was examined. In all studies included, premature infants with a gestational age <28 weeks were randomly assigned to a low (85-89%) or a high (91-95%) SpO₂ target group. A total of 4911 children were examined in the study. The results of the meta-analysis show, that in the low SpO₂ target group the risk for mortality (RR = 1.41, 95% CI = 1.14-1.74) and necrotizing enterocolitis (RR = 1.25, 95% CI = 1.05-1.49) was significantly increased (RR = relative risk compared to the high SpO₂ target group). In the high SpO₂ target group the risk for severe retinopathy of prematurity (RR = 0.74, 95% CI = 0.59-0.92) was significantly increased (Saugstad & Aune, 2013). Based on these findings Saugstad and Aune (2013) recommend a target range of functional SpO₂ “at 90%-95% in infants with gestational age < 28 weeks until 36 weeks postmenstrual age”. Another challenge lies in the first 10 minutes after birth, as the oxygen saturation rises steadily during this period (Dawson & Morley, 2010). Dawson et al. (2010) provide percentiles of SpO₂ level during the first 10 minutes after birth, which can be used as an orientation for a dynamically changing target range. In premature infants the increase of SpO₂ is significantly slower than in term infants (Dawson et al., 2010). Dawson et al. (2010) showed that 5 minutes after birth, the median SpO₂ for preterm infants was 86% and for term infants 92%. Accordingly, already within the first 10 minutes after birth it is important for preterm infants to ensure that SpO₂ values are not too high and lie within a specific though dynamically changing range.

1.2.6.2 Sonifications of conventional pulse oximeters

The first sonification for pulse oximetry was presented in 1983 by the Nellcor Corporation. This sonification produces a tone with every heartbeat, with the frequency varying according to the oxygen saturation. With an increase or decrease in oxygen saturation, the frequency also increases or decreases respectively (Schulte &

Block, 1992). This fundamental sonification design can still be found in most pulse oximeters today.

A pulse tone with a variable pitch seems to have advantages over a fixed pitch. In a study with 30 anaesthetists the response time to a simulated oxygen desaturation could be shortened via a variable pitch pulse oximeter compared to a fixed pitch pulse oximeter (Craven & McIndoe, 1999). Furthermore, it seems to be beneficial to use a logarithmic mapping between SpO₂ and the frequency of the pulse tone compared to a linear mapping. Schulte and Block (1992) tested whether changes in pulse frequency were detected when using a pulse oximeter with a linear mapping. The frequency of the pulse tone decreased by 5 Hz with each decrease of SpO₂ by one percent. Schulte and Block (1992) reported that only 67% of the participants noticed a change in SpO₂ from 98- to 97% and therefore suggest the use of a logarithmic scale. Also Morris and Mohacsi (2005) could show, that anaesthetists had problems in estimating SpO₂ changes when using a pulse oximeter with a linear mapping between SpO₂ and frequency. Brown, Edworthy, Sneyd, and Schlesinger (2015) examined whether a linear or logarithmic mapping between SpO₂ and frequency informs the listener more accurately about the current SpO₂ value. The results show that the participants (40 anaesthetists) were significantly more accurate in estimating absolute SpO₂ values and the size of SpO₂ level differences with a logarithmic scale than with a linear scale. Brown et al. (2015) thus argue for the use of logarithmic scales such as a semitone scale.

Why would anyone use a linear scale? OF COURSE you need a logarithmic scale

The sonification of commercial pulse oximeters does not seem to be standardized. Santamore and Cleaver (2003) analyzed the acoustic properties of four different pulse oximeter models. For all SpO₂ values between 80- and 100%, the tested models produced different pulse tone frequencies. In a later study, Loeb, Brecknell, and Sanderson (2016) analyzed the acoustic properties of 21 commercial pulse oximeters. Considerable differences were observed between the individual models in terms of the frequency range for SpO₂ values between 1-100%, the number of harmonic overtones of the pulse tones, the type of mapping between SpO₂ and the frequency of the pulse tones (linear or logarithmic) and the use of specific SpO₂ thresholds (Loeb et al., 2016). This lack of standardization can further complicate the interpretation of the pulse sounds.

In fact, there seem to be problems in correctly interpreting the pulse sounds of commercial pulse oximeters. In particular, this could be shown in preterm infants, who were treated at a neonatal intensive care unit (NICU). Sink, Hope, and Hagadorn (2011) examined how well a specified SpO₂ target range (85-92%) could be achieved in premature infants in a NICU. 14 children with a gestational age of <29 weeks were examined in the study. On average, the SpO₂ level was within the target range in only 16.1% (median) of the examined period. A significant factor was the number of patients per nurse. For example, with an one-to-one care (one patient per

nurse) the SpO₂ level could be kept within the target range for 38% of the time and only for 22% of the time with an assignment of two patients per nurse. Lim et al. (2014) examined 45 preterm infants with a gestational age <37 weeks who were treated at a NICU. The SpO₂ target range (88-92%) was only achieved for 31% of the whole study period, whereas prolonged periods of hyperoxia or hypoxia were observed. Ruiz, Trzaski, Sink, and Hagadorn (2014) could observe an over-documentation of the SpO₂ target range by the staff in very low birth weight infants at a NICU. Finally, White et al. (2017) examined whether SpO₂ levels in children with a gestational age of <32 weeks remain within the target ranges as defined by the International Neonatal Resuscitation Guidelines in the first 10 minutes after birth. According to White et al. (2017) the SpO₂ level deviated from the target ranges for almost two thirds of the first 10 minutes after birth.

Apart from hiring additional staff, the use of a different sound design for the pulse oximeter could help to keep SpO₂ within predefined target ranges. Although a variable pitch is helpful in detecting changes in SpO₂ levels, it is difficult to determine the range of the current SpO₂ value. As described in chapter 1.2.6.1 it is very important for the well-being of a preterm infant to keep the SpO₂ level in a specific target range. The sonification of the pulse oximeter should therefore inform the clinician without ambiguity whether the current SpO₂ level is within, above or below the target range. However, unless one has absolute pitch (see Deutsch, 2012) determining the current SpO₂ level from the variable pitch of the pulse tone alone is a very difficult task.

1.2.6.3 Novel sound designs for the pulse oximeter

In the recent years researchers have proposed novel sonifications for pulse oximetry. In the following, an overview of the different approaches and study results will be given. In a recent paper Paterson, Sanderson, Paterson, and Loeb (2019) evaluated an enhanced sonification over the course of several studies. SpO₂ was divided into the three ranges target (100-97%), low (96-90%) and critical (89-80%). For the enhanced as well as the conventional sonification a logarithmic mapping between SpO₂ and the frequency of the pulse tone was used, whereas the frequency increased with increasing SpO₂ level. For the enhanced sonification, the sound was changed in the low and critical range by adding tremolo to the pulse tones. In addition, brightness of the pulse tones was increased in the critical range. In summary it could be shown, that adding acoustic stimuli like tremolo and brightness to a conventional sonification of pulse oximetry helps to monitor SpO₂ levels (Paterson, Sanderson, Paterson, Liu, & Loeb, 2016a, 2016b; Paterson, Sanderson, Paterson, & Loeb, 2017; Paterson et al., 2019). This was also the case when the participants were engaged in a distractor task in the visual (Paterson et al., 2016b; Paterson et al., 2017; Paterson et al., 2019) and auditory modality (Paterson et al., 2019) and when background

noise was present (Paterson et al., 2017). Even clinicians who were familiar with the sonification of conventional pulse oximeters, performed better with the enhanced sonification (Paterson et al., 2019).

Considering the present study, approaches that are designed to monitor the oxygen saturation of premature infants are of particular interest. Hinckfuss, Sanderson, Loeb, Liley, and Liu (2016) proposed a new sound design for pulse oximetry intended for monitoring preterm infants. In fact two alternative sonifications were proposed and compared with a control sonification in two separate experiments. A conventional pulse oximeter was used for the control sonification using a logarithmic mapping between SpO₂ and the pitch of the pulse tones. The first redesign used a logarithmic mapping between SpO₂ and pitch just like in the control condition. The pitch difference for a certain change in SpO₂ varied in dependence of the SpO₂ range. These were very small within the target range and became larger outside the target range with increasing distance between the SpO₂ value and the midpoint of the target range. A reference tone was added for the second redesign, if the SpO₂ value was outside the target range. This reference tone preceded every fourth pulse, with its pitch corresponding to an SpO₂ value of 93% (the midpoint of the target range). Thus the relative pitch of the reference tone indicated whether the SpO₂ value was above or below the target range. For both experiments the oxygen saturation was divided into the following five ranges: Very low (80-83.5%), low (83.5-89.5%), target (89.5-95.5%), high (95.5-98.5%) and very high (89.5-100%). The participants were asked to determine SpO₂ ranges and also to categorize the change in SpO₂ level as increasing or decreasing. For the first redesign, there was no significant difference to the conventional sonification for both outcome measures. For the second redesign, participants detected SpO₂ ranges significantly more accurately with the sonification using a reference tone ($M = 85\%$, $SD = 16\%$) than with the control sonification ($M = 60\%$, $SD = 13\%$). Furthermore, with the enhanced sonification ($Mdn = 96\%$) the direction of SpO₂ change was detected significantly more accurately than with the control sonification ($Mdn = 94\%$).

In a subsequent study Deschamps et al. (2016) proposed another sonification for monitoring SpO₂ levels of preterm infants. For the redesign different levels of tremolo were added to a conventional sonification, which used a logarithmic mapping between SpO₂ and pitch. As in the study by Hinckfuss et al. (2016), the oxygen saturation was divided into five ranges (see above). No tremolo was implemented in the target range. Three cycles of tremolo per tone were added in the adjacent ranges above and below the target range and six cycles of tremolo per tone were added in the ranges of very low or very high oxygen saturation. Also, the sonification using a reference tone as proposed by Hinckfuss et al. (2016) was tested. The results show that SpO₂ ranges as well as transitions into and out of the target range were detected significantly more accurately with the „tremolo-sonification” ($Mdn = 94\%$, $Mdn =$

96%, respectively) and with the sonification using a reference tone ($Mdn = 81\%$, $Mdn = 100\%$, respectively) than with the control sonification ($Mdn = 52\%$, $Mdn = 71\%$, respectively). As explained above, monitoring oxygen saturation in the first 10 minutes after birth is another challenge, as the SpO_2 target range changes with every minute (Zestic, Brecknell, Liley, & Sanderson, 2019). In a study by Zestic et al. (2019), an attempt was made to design a sonification that would show the clinician whether the current SpO_2 level is within a dynamically changing target range. Oxygen saturation was divided into the ranges high, target and low. If the current SpO_2 value left the target range, tremolo was added to the pulse tones of a conventional pulse oximeter, using a logarithmic mapping between pitch and SpO_2 level. More precisely three cycles of tremolo were added for the low range and five cycles of tremolo for the high range. Additionally the brightness of the pulse tones was increased for the high range. Results show that SpO_2 ranges could be identified significantly more accurately with the enhanced sonification ($M = 92\%$, $SD = 7\%$) than with the conventional sonification ($M = 62\%$, $SD = 9\%$).

The sonification using a reference tone, as proposed by Hinckfuss et al. (2016), should unambiguously convey the information about SpO_2 values being above or below the target range, at least from a theoretical point of view. The presence of the reference tone indicates SpO_2 deviations from the target range and its relative pitch indicates, if SpO_2 values lie above or below the target range. Deschamps et al. (2016) could improve the identification of SpO_2 level by adding different levels of tremolo to a conventional sonification of pulse oximetry. However, whether the current SpO_2 value is above or below the target range is conveyed to the listener in the same way as with conventional sonifications. The listener must rely solely on the absolute pitch of the pulse tones, which can be problematic. Zestic et al. (2019) addressed this problem by additionally increasing the brightness of the pulse tones above the target range.

In the studies described so far, the identification of SpO_2 levels was facilitated by acoustic cues that were added stepwise to the sound of the pulse tones. However, it might be possible that in particular the identification of continuous SpO_2 values could be communicated to the listener even more effectively via the gradual or continuous change in acoustic properties of the pulse tones. A study by Collett, Salisbury, Loeb, and Sanderson (2019) therefore investigated whether absolute SpO_2 values can be identified more accurately with a sonification using a stepwise change in its acoustic properties, or by a sonification using a continuous change in its acoustic properties. The oxygen saturation was divided into the ranges target (100-97%), low (96-90%) and critical (89-80%). Both sonifications tested here used a logarithmic mapping between pitch and SpO_2 . For the sonification with a stepwise change of its acoustic properties, five tremolo cycles per tone were added in the low range and eight tremolo cycles per tone were added in the critical range. In addition, brightness

of the pulse tones was increased in the critical range. In contrast, a continuous change in the acoustic properties of the tones was achieved by gradually increasing tremolo in the low range as SpO₂ decreased. The brightness of the tones gradually increased in the critical range with a decreasing level of SpO₂, whereas tremolo remained constant. Results show that the accuracy of identifying absolute SpO₂ values was significantly better for a sonification with a stepwise change of acoustic properties ($M = 53.7\%$, $SD = 12.2\%$) than for a sonification with a continuous change of acoustic properties ($M = 47.9\%$, $SD = 11.7\%$). The participants also performed significantly better at identifying target transitions and SpO₂ ranges, if the acoustic properties of the tones were changed in a stepwise way. According to Collett et al. (2019), the results can be explained by the fact that stepwise changes in the tones provide clearer and more pronounced auditory cues for the current SpO₂ range and range transitions. This is an important finding for future sonifications. Nevertheless both approaches could be used complementary. A stepwise change of the pulse tones could be complemented by a continuous change of an additional psychoacoustic dimension.

1.3 The sonifications of the present study

The present work proposes a novel psychoacoustic sonification for the pulse oximeter. Compared to previous approaches the psychoacoustic sonification is designed to provide the listener with information about the current oxygen saturation at an even higher level of accuracy, while still clearly communicating important SpO₂ thresholds. This objective is addressed by combining a stepwise with a continuous change of psychoacoustic parameters. A stepwise approach is used to make important thresholds apparent to the listener, while a continuous change is supposed to provide a fine grained resolution of the oxygen saturation. In addition, a sonification based on the model of a conventional pulse oximeter is developed and used for the control condition in the listening test of the present study. Finally, an alternative sonification is being developed with the aim of taking the perceived pleasantness in the sound design into account. In the present study, the oxygen saturation is subdivided into seven ranges (see Figure 8). Ranges 2 to 6 lie within the optimal range of 90-95% SpO₂, while range 1 lies above and range 7 lies below the optimal range. In contrast to other studies (see chapter 1.2.6), the target area is divided into five further ranges. The psychoacoustic sonification design is intended to allow the differentiation of a larger number of SpO₂ ranges and thus to achieve a more accurate resolution of the target area. Here, it is assumed that it may be important for the clinician to be able to hear whether the oxygen saturation is in the center or more in the upper or lower part of the target range.

Figure 8. Division of the oxygen saturation into seven ranges. The optimum range lies between 90 - 95%. The corresponding saturation range is provided on the left of each colour-coded area.

1.3.1 A psychoacoustic sonification

1.3.1.1 Sonification design

A Shepard tone is used as the basis for the sonification. In a study by Ziemer and Schultheis (2018a), a Shepard tone was used successfully for a navigation task, where the speed of the rising or falling tone indicated the distance to a target in one of two dimensions (see also Ziemer et al., 2017; Ziemer & Schultheis, 2018b). Therefore it is considered that the Shepard tone might also be useful in estimating the distance of the instantaneous SpO₂ from a target region. The Shepard tone used in the present study contains six partials, whose frequency is defined as:

$$f_n = f_0 2^n \text{Hz}, \quad (3)$$

where $n = 0, \dots, N-1$ and $N = 6$. The lowest partial f_0 is equal to 100 Hz. For SpO₂ values above the center range the frequency of the partials is rising and for SpO₂ values below the center range their frequency is falling. This way a simple binary coding is used to convey the information about SpO₂ being below or above the center of the target range. The rising or falling motion of the partials follows the following function:

$$f(\phi) = f_0 \sqrt[12]{2^{\frac{\phi 12N}{2\pi}}}. \quad (4)$$

Two adjacent partials thus always have a distance of one octave. Here $\sqrt[12]{2}$ was

chosen as the basis of the exponential function, since the sonification is based on a semitone scale of a twelve-tone equal temperament tuning system (see the following chapter). The phase ϕ increases for a rising motion of the partials continuously from 0 to 2π such that within one period the frequency of the lowest partial increases from f_0 to f_N . The phase ϕ is defined as:

$$\phi(\theta, t) = \arg[\sin(2\pi\theta t)]. \quad (5)$$

θ is a function of the distance between the current SpO₂ value and the center of the target range. The greater the distance, the faster the frequency of the partials changes. As in the study by Shepard (1964), the partials move through a bell-shaped curve, which weights the amplitude of the partials. The amplitude gradually approaches zero as the partials approach f_0 or f_N . To give the Shepard tone a pulse-like sound, a temporal envelope curve is used. Within one pulse the Shepard tone moves through a frequency interval, which is determined by its speed. With increasing speed of the Shepard tone, the frequency interval becomes larger. This way a continuous mapping between the SpO₂ distance to the center of the target range and the frequency interval within a pulse tone is provided. Since the phase of the Shepard tone provides no additional information about the current SpO₂ value, the Shepard tone is reset to the starting point of its period for each pulse.

To indicate that the current SpO₂ value is within the target range (90-95%) a background noise is presented, which sounds continuously and thus not only within the time window of each pulse. This way the most important information about the current oxygen saturation can be conveyed to the listener, while the cognitive workload is kept to a minimum. Here pink noise is used, which is further filtered by a comb filter (see chapter 2.4 for more details). Further information about the current SpO₂ value is provided by the movement of the Shepard tone. A rising or falling motion of the Shepard tone indicates SpO₂ values above and below the center range respectively. Within the center range the speed of the Shepard tone is set to 0, which results in a pulse of constant frequency. However, in the target range (90-95%), two further ranges above (range 2 and 3) and below (range 5 and 6) the center range are to be distinguished (see Figure 8). In order to identify these ranges the listener must rely on the size of the frequency interval that the Shepard tone passes through within one pulse. The speed of the Shepard tone and thus also the size of the frequency interval reach their maximum at 90- and 95% of SpO₂. Leaving the target range is indicated by the discontinuation of the background noise. In addition, roughness of the Shepard tone is increased, both above and below the target range.

1.3.1.2 Psychoacoustic background

In the following, the psychoacoustic background of the continuous change of the sonification as a function of the oxygen saturation is explained, whereby the Shepard tone is the central element of this translation. Furthermore, the psychoacoustic background of the stepwise changes of the sonification, more precisely the use of the background noise and the change in the roughness of the Shepard tone is discussed.

In a listening experiment Shepard (1964) could show a circularity in the judgement of relative pitch, which provides evidence that pitch can be separated in the two components height and tonality or chroma. The complex tones generated by Shepard preserved tonality but could not be ordered with respect to height. This finding suggests that the perceived pitch is not adequately represented by a rectilinear scale. In fact the tones could be arranged equidistantly around a circle in such a way, that the next clockwise tone is perceived higher in pitch while the next counterclockwise tone is perceived lower in pitch (Shepard, 1964). This way the Shepard tone can create the illusion of an infinitely rising or falling pitch, while the fundamental octave of the perceived pitch remains ambiguous (Ziemer et al., 2017). Although this illusion cannot be heard with the psychoacoustic sonification, the Shepard tone provides a number of advantages. Auditory brightness and loudness of the Shepard tone remain rather constant, so that these variables can be used for other input parameters (Ziemer et al., 2017). For the present sonification both brightness and loudness of the pulse tones do not provide the listener with any relevant information.

Therefore, a change of brightness or loudness could be false

in the data underlying the sonification. As the She

parameters nearly constant, possible confusion is a

Based on evidence on auditory scene analysis (see Br

that the partials of the Shepard tone are integrat

explained by Ziemer et al. (2017), the carrier frequencies fuse because they are separated by octaves (see also chapter 1.1.9.3). The octave interval between the carrier frequencies is maintained even when their frequency is rising or falling. Here the principle of common fate is important. The frequency of the carriers changes in synchrony, facilitating their grouping by the auditory system (Ziemer et al., 2017). This principle applies also in case of the FM modulated Shepard tone – roughness of the Shepard tone was increased by using FM synthesis (see chapter 2.4) –, as the frequency of the carrier frequencies and of the generated sidebands vary in synchrony. Moreover, these sidebands do not form a harmonic spectrum, since each carrier frequency is modulated with the same modulation frequency (Ziemer et al., 2017). In case the sidebands would form a harmonic spectrum, they could get integrated into a second auditory stream. This would make it difficult for the listener to capture the information conveyed by the sonification, due to the difficulty of following several streams simultaneously (Ziemer et al., 2017). Last but not least

You forgot to mention that all partials of the Shepard tone serve as “carrier” frequencies (that will eventually be modulated by a modulator frequency to create roughness).

the sonification of a pulse oximeter is presented in mono via a single loudspeaker. This facilitates the grouping into one stream, as the partials of the Shepard tone all originate from the same location in space (see chapter 1.1.9, Ziemer et al., 2017).

It is very likely that the individual pulse tones get integrated into one single stream by the auditory system. Again the common spatial location of the pulse tones facilitates the formation of a stream. Also the temporal proximity of the pulse tones helps the auditory system to group the individual pulses. Another important factor that influences the grouping into different streams is the similarity between the pulse tones. All pulse tones share the same carrier frequencies and duration and for every pulse tone the phase of the Shepard tone is set to 0. Moreover the loudness and the brightness of the Shepard tone remains fairly constant for every tone. The frequency interval the Shepard tone passes through varies continuously as a function of the SpO₂ level. As SpO₂ level is expected to change in a continuous manner without large and sudden jumps, the interval of the pulse tones should only change slowly and gradually, which facilitates integration according to the principle of continuity. A sudden change of the sound quality occurs, when the SpO₂ level is leaving the target range, as the roughness of the Shepard tone is increased. According to Bregman (1990) the factors that influence grouping processes of auditory scene analysis can reinforce and compete with each other. For the auditory system, the sudden change in roughness should be an indication of new event in the environment. The new event is that the current SpO₂ deviates from the optimum range. However, there are still many factors that support an integration of the pulse tones, so that they are perceived as a continuation of the previous pulse tones within the optimum range. Last but not least, all of the factors mentioned here support the integration of the pulse tones into a single stream also facilitates the separation between the pulse tones and other sounds in the environment.

In practice, this is of major importance, as other devices produce tonal pulses, too. For example telephones ring, electrical devices indicate status or malfunctions, etc.

The central parameter of the sonification is pitch. As described in chapter 1.3.1.1 the pitch changes depending on the current oxygen saturation. The listener must be able to tell from the direction of the pitch change whether the oxygen saturation is above or below the center range. In addition, the magnitude of the change provides information about the distance of the current oxygen saturation to the center (92.5%) of the target range. By intuition, it should be possible to understand that a rising motion of the Shepard tone indicates a deviation of SpO₂ above the center range and a falling motion of the Shepard tone indicates a deviation of SpO₂ below the center range. This principle is also similar to the sonification of a conventional pulse oximeter, where an increase in oxygen saturation is accompanied by an increase in the frequency of the pulse tones. A positive polarity is chosen between the size of the frequency interval that the Shepard tone passes through and the distance of the current SpO₂ value from the center range. Again, this relationship should be intuitively understandable, as a musical interval can be understood as the relative

distance between two tones in terms of their frequencies. The selection of pitch as the central parameter of the sonification represents an optimal choice, as the human auditory system is very sensitive to changes in pitch (see chapter 1.1). The just noticeable variation in frequency (JNVF) is almost constant at a value of about 3.6 Hz for a modulation frequency of 4 Hz and carrier frequencies below 500 Hz (for a level of 60 phon). Above 500 Hz the JNFV is about 0.7% of the carrier frequency. This allows a sensation of very small changes in frequency, especially in the medium to high frequency range. At 50 Hz the JNVF is about 120 Cent, which is about a semitone in music. Cent is a logarithmic unit, which can be used to quantify musical intervals (see Ellis & Hipkins, 1884). At 400 Hz the JNVF is at 10 Cent, much smaller than the interval of a semitone. The human auditory system is therefore able to sense very small changes in pitch. For the sonification of other parameters like sound pressure level are also important (see chapter 2.4) but these are not varied in this sonification. Besides, it is generally unadvisable to use parameters that are not orthogonal to each other in the same sonification.

I think you did not use this term before. Maybe a visualization of the Shepard tone that shows this bell-shaped curve would be beneficial.

In the psychoacoustic sonification, the change in pitch depends on the speed at which the partials of the Shepard tone move through their **bell shaped envelope curve**. In the center range (range 4) the speed is set to 0, such that the pitch is constant in this range. Since the auditory system is very sensitive to changes in pitch, a constant pitch among other rising or falling tones should be easy to identify. In the center range the phase ϕ of the Shepard tones is set to 0° , so that $f_0 = 100$ Hz, $f_1 = 200$ Hz, $f_2 = 400$ Hz, etc.. For instance, a change in frequency of $f_2 = 400$ Hz by 3.6 Hz (see above) would correspond to a change in oxygen saturation of slightly above 0.01%, if one tracks back the processing chain described in chapter 2.4. In general, the change in frequency is 10 Cent for a change in oxygen saturation of 0.01%. Changes in oxygen saturation on this scale are probably not relevant from a practical point of view. In the present study, the participants are supposed to detect a change in oxygen saturation of 0.1% (see chapter 2). A change in oxygen saturation of 0.1% gives a change in frequency of 100 Cent, which is a semitone with a frequency ratio of $\sqrt[12]{2}$. For the lowest partial $f_0 = 100$ Hz a change in oxygen saturation of 0.1% results in a change of its frequency by about 6 Hz, which is above the JNVF as reported above. In general, it may be beneficial to assign a relevant SpO₂ change (here 0.1%) to a specific musical interval (here a semitone) (see Brown et al., 2015). This also takes into account the fact that the perception of pitch is logarithmic rather than linear in nature, as reflected in the mel scale (Fastl & Zwicker, p. 113). Also, Brown et al. (2015) showed that anaesthetists were able to estimate absolute SpO₂ values and differences in SpO₂ levels significantly more accurately with a logarithmic pitch scale than with a linear pitch scale. At a SpO₂ value of 90%, i.e. a deviation of 2.5% from the center of the target range, the interval comprises 2500 Cent, which is equivalent to two octaves and one semitone.

Scaling decisions are based on the aim to provide a fine grained resolution of the instantaneous SpO_2 value and to provide a meaningful change in frequency for a certain change in SpO_2 . This is achieved in that even a slight change of 0.1% in oxygen saturation results in a perceptible change of the interval the Shepard tone passes through. A change in oxygen saturation by 0.1% always leads to an increase or decrease of the interval by a semitone.

The JNVF serves only as an orientation. The frequency modulation used by Fastl and Zwicker (2007) is obviously different from a rising or falling Shepard tone. For example, the JNVFs mentioned here refer to a modulation frequency of 4 Hz. At higher modulation frequencies, the JNVFs are significantly larger (see Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 185). Similarly, the JNVF could depend on the speed of the Shepard tone, which is varied in the psychoacoustic sonification. Furthermore, the partials of the Shepard tone form a harmonic spectrum, i.e. they differ from individual sine tones. A change in frequency can be noticed via frequency changes of all partials. In any case the human auditory system has a very high frequency resolution. Up to 16 kHz the human auditory system can distinguish 640 adjacent pitches, which was calculated on the basis of just-noticeable frequency variations (Zwicker & Fastl, 2017, p. 184). Therefore, changes in the frequency of the partials of the Shepard tone should be easily detected by the listener. Perceiving chroma or tonality is limited to the audible frequency range below about 5000 Hz (Gelfand, 2009, p. 223). It is important that the listener is able to hear a change in chroma, as a change of SpO_2 of 0.1% corresponds to a fixed musical interval. The partials of the Shepard tone should therefore always sufficiently cover the frequency range below 5000 Hz. This is the case with the present sonification, since the highest partial has a frequency of 3200 Hz.

The sonification principle is designed to be continuous. A continuous increase in oxygen saturation results in a continuous increase in the frequency interval every pulse goes through. In contrast to the sonification of conventional pulse oximeters, this sonification provides a reference value. The Shepard tone is reset to the starting point of its period for each pulse tone. This starting point provides a reference for the listener to estimate the size of the interval. As described in chapter 1.3.1.1 a continuous background noise can be heard within the target range. Here pink noise is used, because it is more pleasant to hear than white noise. Pink noise has been used, for example, to improve sleep quality (Papalambros et al., 2017). An increased pleasantness of the background noise is particularly important, if patients or staff are exposed to the sounds of the sonification over a long period of time. The pink noise was further filtered by a comb filter to create a more artificial sound. This is to better distinguish the noise from other noise sources, such as respiratory machines or air conditioning systems. The use of the comb filter increases the probability of producing a distinguishable timbre compared to other background noises. Besides

the spatial information – the noise originates from the loudspeaker of the pulse oximeter and not from any other machines – a different timbre provides an additional cue that allows a stream segregation between the pink noise of this sonification and other possible background noise. Furthermore, masking of the sonification by other noise sources becomes more difficult.

It is important that for critical SpO₂ values the sonification conveys the urgency to act. The roughness of the Shepard tone is increased by FM synthesis below 90 and above 95% of SpO₂. The number and amplitudes of sidebands generated by FM synthesis depend on the modulation depth (see chapter 2.4). Increasing the modulation depth increases “the number and amplitudes of inharmonic frequency components” and thus the perceived roughness and the perceived inharmonicity and noisiness (Ziemer et al., 2017, p. 6). An increased inharmonicity is generally perceived as more urgent (Edworthy, 2003). The sonification thus indicates a higher need for action for SpO₂ values outside the target range. As described in chapter 2.4 a modulation frequency of 120 Hz and a modulation depth of 100 Hz is used. For a pure tone with a center frequency of 1500 Hz, a sound pressure level of 70 dB_{SPL} and a frequency deviation of ± 700 Hz a maximum roughness can be achieved for a modulation frequency of about 70 Hz (Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 260). Roughness also increases approximately linearly with the logarithm of the frequency deviation (Δf). Thus, larger values of Δf and a lower modulation frequency could achieve higher levels of roughness. On the one hand, by further increasing the roughness for SpO₂ values outside the target range, it would be even easier to distinguish two levels of roughness used in this sonification. On the other hand, an increased inharmonicity and noisiness leads to a lower pitch strength (see chapter 1.1.3). This could negatively affect the perception of pitch change of the Shepard tone. However the direction of pitch change is essential to decide whether the current SpO₂ value is above or below the target range.

In order to ensure that the listener still reliably detects SpO₂ values outside the target range, a redundant coding is chosen. The listener can hear SpO₂ deviations from the target range by either detecting an increased level of roughness or the discontinuation of the background noise. A redundant coding can increase the robustness of an auditory display, as it can make important thresholds more obvious to the user (Ferguson et al., 2006). By changing the acoustic properties of the pulse tones continuously within the target range the listeners attention is not attracted in an unfavourable manner, allowing him/her to engage in additional tasks. When the SpO₂ value leaves the target range the sound quality of the sonification shows a sudden change, as both the roughness of the Shepard tone is increased and the background noise is not present anymore. This way the attention of the listener is directed to the sonification in the case of critical SpO₂ values. Last but not least the envelope of the Shepard tone is symmetrical around its maximum. The maxi-

units should be in plain letters, not in italics... otherwise, “dB” reads d times B. You can use \text or \mathrm

mum in this sonification is at 800 Hz, thus avoiding excess of high frequency energy. This also avoids a strong sensation of sharpness, which would reduce the sensory pleasantness of the sonification (see Fastl & Zwicker, 2007, p. 243).

1.3.2 A conventional sonification

For the control condition of the present study a sonification is used, which is based on a conventional pulse oximeter. Here the model MX800 from the manufacturer Philips is chosen. The model MX800 is chosen because it uses a logarithmic mapping between SpO₂ and frequency, which is advantageous compared to a linear mapping for monitoring oxygen saturation (see e.g. Brown et al., 2015). The fundamental frequency of the MX800 is at 662 Hz for an oxygen saturation of 100%, whereas the frequency remains constant within one pulse beat. With each 1% decrease in oxygen saturation, the frequency decreases by 2.9% (Loeb et al., 2016). In the present study, the fundamental frequency is varied as a function of oxygen saturation as follows:

$$y[\text{Hz}] = 662 (0.971^x), \quad (6)$$

where y is the fundamental frequency and $x = 100 - s$, with s being equal to the current SpO₂ value. For an oxygen saturation of 80% this results in a fundamental frequency of about 367 Hz. According to a spectrogram created by Loeb et al. (2016), a pulse tone of the MX800 model consists of the fundamental frequency and four higher harmonics. Therefore, four higher harmonics are used in the present study, with their amplitude decreasing with increasing frequency. Furthermore, an alarm is added for SpO₂ values outside the optimal range, although Loeb et al. (2016) report no alarm for the MX800 model. The sound design of the alarm is based on a study by Paterson et al. (2019), where a similar alarm was used for the control condition. Using an alarm for critical SpO₂ values is typical for the sonification of many conventional pulse oximeters. In intensive care units, the variable pitch is often deactivated to reduce the noise level so that only the alarm can be heard (Paterson et al., 2019). Paterson et al. (2019) also showed that subjects could identify SpO₂ ranges and absolute SpO₂ values more accurately when using a sonification with a variable pitch and an alarm, than when using a sonification with a variable pitch but no alarm. Therefore, by using a logarithmic mapping between frequency and SpO₂ and an alarm for critical SpO₂ values, the most promising variant of a conventional sonification is used. The alarm consists of three short tones, whereas each of the tones lasts about 400 ms and has a fundamental frequency of 530 Hz. The alarm sounds once, as soon as the oxygen saturation leaves the optimum range, i.e. if the oxygen saturation exceeds a value of 95% or falls below a value of 90%. At a fundamental frequency of 530 Hz the alarm can be clearly distinguished from the pulse tones of the sonification. At 95% SpO₂ the fundamental frequency of the pulse tones lies at about 571 Hz and at 90% SpO₂ at about 493 Hz. With a JND

of about 1 Hz at a frequency of about 500 Hz the distance in frequency is large enough to avoid confusion with the alarm. Also, the roughness of the alarm tone is increased, providing an additional cue for segregation from the other pulse tones of the sonification. As for the psychoacoustic sonification, the increased inharmonicity of the alarm tone should increase the perceived urgency to act.

1.3.3 An alternative sonification

As described above, the sonification of a pulse oximeter has a monitoring function, which requires a continuous or frequent auditory output. Therefore it is important to ensure, that the user does not get annoyed or tired by listening to the sonification (Vickers, 2011). An increased emphasis on aesthetic considerations could reduce listener fatigue, increase the perceived pleasantness and also facilitate the interpretation of the sonification. The sound of a pulse oximeter is often perceived as annoying by clinical staff. For example, the variable pitch of a pulse oximeter is frequently switched off in intensive care units, so that only the alarm for critical SpO₂ values is heard (Paterson et al., 2019). This is a trivial example of the fact that the functionality of a sonification can be limited by the lack of aesthetic considerations.

The alternative sonification is based on samples from the *Electronic music studios* (2019) of the University of Iowa and the software *Halion 6* (2017). The samples are recordings of the instruments double bass, guitar, violin and piccolo flute. The aesthetic consideration underlying this choice is rather simple. A central reason for choosing musical instruments is the familiarity of their sound. The so-called mere exposure effect suggests that a repeated exposure to a stimulus will result in a more positive evaluation of that stimulus (Zajonc, 1968). This effect can be observed in a variety of areas, as music or art (Bornstein & Craver-Lemley, 2017). Familiar sounds should consequently be evaluated more positively than artificial and less familiar sounds. It should be noted, that for hospital staff, the opposite effect may apply. Since the staff is often exposed to the sounds of conventional pulse oximeters, alternatives may be judged more negatively.

This sonification is based on a similar sonification principle as the psychoacoustic sonification. It is based equally on psychoacoustic considerations and it is not assumed that the two sonifications differ in how well information about the current oxygen saturation is transmitted to the listener. The instruments differentiate the seven ranges of oxygen saturation. In range 1 a flute can be heard, in range 2 and 3 a violin, in range 4, 5 and 6 a guitar and in range 7 a double bass. The identification of a musical instrument thus already provides important information about the current SpO₂ value. The onset (or transient) of a tone is crucial for the identification of musical instruments (see Elliott, 1975; Siedenbug, 2019). Therefore it is important not to manipulate the onset of the sample, to ensure that the instru-

ments can be correctly identified by the listener. The assignment of the instruments to the different ranges is based on their timbre. According to the *Acoustical Society of America* (2020) timbre can be defined as “that multidimensional attribute of auditory sensation which enables a listener to judge that two non-identical sounds, similarly presented and having the same loudness, pitch, spatial location, and duration, are dissimilar”. Iverson and Krumhansel (1993) investigated the characteristics of a sound that influence timbre. Participants of this study rated the similarity of tones of different instruments. Via multidimensional scaling, the instruments were arranged with respect to their similarity. Via the horizontal dimension, percussive instruments were spatially separated from blown instruments, while the vertical dimension arranged the instruments according to their brightness. The vertical brightness dimension of the similarity judgements (Iverson & Krumhansl, 1993) correlated strongly with the spectral centroid of the presented tones ($|r| \geq 0.61$ for all experiments). In the present study the instruments are assigned to the different SpO₂ ranges in such a way that the spectral centroid and thus the perceived brightness increases with an increasing level of oxygen saturation. Percussive instruments could be separated from wind instruments via the second dimension identified by Iverson and Krumhansel (1993). The similarity judgements on this dimension could be explained by differences in the amplitude envelopes of the tones. In the present study, the amplitude envelopes of sounds within the target range should be audibly different from those outside the target range. Violin and guitar notes are plucked, while the double bass is bowed and the piccolo flute is blown. The tones within the target range therefore show a fast decay in amplitude, while the tones outside the target range are rather stationary. Note, that for the alternative sonification the actual duration of the pulse tones is slightly longer than 375 ms. The decay in amplitude is a little flatter to make the sound of the instruments more natural. Since the principle of changing the pitch in dependence of the oxygen saturation is identical to the psychoacoustic sonification, it will not be explained any further here.

1.4 Objectives and hypotheses

The main objective of the present study is the development and evaluation of a sonification for monitoring preterm infants via a pulse oximeter. The sound designs of the proposed sonifications are developed under consideration of findings from the field of psychoacoustics. This is considered necessary to design a sonification that is intuitively understood by the listener and can convey information in a predictable way. For the psychoacoustic sonification, a stepwise approach is combined with a continuous approach. In this way, the sonification conveys critical SpO₂ ranges as well as a very accurate resolution of oxygen saturation. In the present study a listening test is conducted to examine how well the SpO₂ ranges as defined in chapter

1.3 can be conveyed to the listener. Both the psychoacoustic and the conventional sonification show a stepwise change in sound when leaving the target area of 90-95% SpO₂. For the psychoacoustic sonification, this is indicated by the absence of the background noise and the increased roughness of the Shepard tone, whereas for the conventional sonification this is indicated by the sound of the alarm. Both forms of tonal change should be easy to recognize for the listener. However, with the conventional sonification, only the absolute pitch of the pulse tones can be used to determine whether the oxygen saturation is above or below the target range. In contrast, the psychoacoustic sonification provides this information by the rising or falling motion of the Shepard tone. Interpreting the absolute pitch is more difficult than identifying a rising or falling pitch of a tone. Furthermore, it is assumed that the SpO₂ ranges within the target range are communicated more accurately with the psychoacoustic than with the conventional sonification. In particular, range 4 should be clearly identifiable via the psychoacoustic sonification. Since the human auditory system is very sensitive to frequency changes, a tone with a constant pitch should be clearly distinguishable from other rising or falling tones. The direction of movement of the Shepard tone can be used to determine whether the oxygen saturation is above or below range 4. The SpO₂ ranges 2 and 3 as well as 5 and 6 must be differentiated from each other by the interval size the Shepard tone moves through within a pulse tone. Here the listener must determine the relative distance of the end point of the rising or falling Shepard tone to its starting point. Thus a relative distance must be determined. In contrast, with the conventional sonification, the ranges within the target area can only be differentiated by estimating the absolute pitch of the pulse tones, which is again a more difficult task. Moreover, the Shepard tone is reset to the starting point of its period for each pulse beat, providing a constant reference point for the listener. On the basis of these considerations the following hypothesis is made:

The seven SpO₂ ranges are identified more accurately with the psychoacoustic sonification than with the conventional sonification.

It is of particular interest if the continuous tonal change of the psychoacoustic sonification can be interpreted by listeners. Thus absolute SpO₂ values between 90- and 95% are estimated by the participants in the listening test of the current study. Within the target range, the interval size that the Shepard tone moves through changes continuously as a function of the current oxygen saturation. As explained above, it is assumed that estimating this interval size is easier than determining the pitch in case of the conventional sonification, since this requires the listener to have absolute pitch. Therefore the following hypothesis is made:

Within the target range, absolute SpO₂ estimates are more accurate with the psychoacoustic sonification than with the conventional sonification.

The sonification of a pulse oximeter has a monitoring function and can be heard

continuously over a relatively long period of time. Therefore, listeners should not get annoyed or tired by the sonification. It is also important that the sonification suits the data and the application context (see chapter 1.2.5). A perceived match between the data and the situational context with the sound characteristics of the sonification could facilitate its interpretation. All sonifications as described in chapter 1.3 are thus evaluated in the listening test with regard to aesthetic aspects, such as the perceived pleasantness and their suitability for pulse oximetry. It is difficult to formulate hypotheses about perceived aesthetic properties on the basis of the theoretical background as discussed in the present paper. Thus, in this regard the study is of an exploratory nature and no hypotheses are formulated.

When designing a sonification, one should also consider who will hear the sonification (Sanderson et al., 2009). According to Walker and Nees (2011), apart from training and experience individual differences determine success in the interpretation of a sonification. Understanding how individual differences in perceptual, cognitive and musical abilities affect the listening performance, allows the design of sonifications that suit most users in a given context (Walker & Nees, 2011). Furthermore, to maximize the probability of success, specific users can be selected for the application of the sonification (Walker & Nees, 2011). It is important to consider the listener's ability to interpret a sonification, as otherwise the listener might be overwhelmed with the task, or the potential of a sonification in conveying information might not be fully exploited. However, such individual determinants have rarely been investigated. Hence, the present study also examines potential predictors for the success in interpreting a sonification. These include the ability and practice to evaluate different forms of sound, the professional involvement with a pulse oximeter and the musical background of the participants. Here again, the study is of an exploratory nature, so that no further hypotheses are made.

2 Method

In the present study an online listening test was conducted. An online experiment was preferred over a laboratory experiment for the following reasons: An online study was considered to be more efficient in recruiting a large number of participants. It was expected to achieve a higher heterogeneity concerning demographic variables, such as age or musical experience, and hence to increase the generalizability of the results. Furthermore, it was of special interest to recruit participants with a medical background, especially people, who had experience with a pulse oximeter. It was assumed that this target group could be recruited more effectively via an online study. The online experiment was conducted in German and was generated using *SoSci Survey* (Leiner, 2019).

2.1 Participants

A total of 66 participants were recruited via personal contacts and online survey platforms. Of all participants, 17 did not complete the study and were therefore excluded from the statistical analysis. Furthermore, 17 participants, who did not correctly answer a question of understanding at the beginning of the study, were also excluded from the statistical analysis. Here participants were asked to click into one of the seven SpO₂ ranges within the optimal range. Understanding this task was considered necessary in order to perform the subsequent listening test. Out of the 32 subjects, who ultimately entered the data analysis, 24 were female (75%) and 8 male (25%), with an average age of 35.2 years ($SD = 15.8$ years). There were three participants with a medical background, including two participants who reported using a pulse oximeter in their daily work. However, only one participant reported dealing with the sounds of a pulse oximeter in her or his daily work. On average participants spent 58.13 minutes ($SD = 107.19$ minutes) per day on interpreting different forms of sound, had 14.09 years ($SD = 17.92$ years) of musical experience and spent 1.34 hours ($SD = 2.35$ hours) playing music per week. The participants did not receive any monetary compensation for participating in the study, participation was based on personal motivation. Prior to the start of the experiment, participants were informed that the experiment could be stopped at any time. In addition, it was pointed out that the data collection is anonymous and that it is not possible to identify individual participants.

2.2 Research design

The type of the sonification represented the experimental manipulation. Here a repeated measures design was used, that is, the participants performed the listening test with both the psychoacoustic and the conventional sonification. If participants

would have performed the listening test with only one sonification, a longer training and a longer listening test would have been possible. In order to make the training as simple as possible, participants were instructed to explore the sonifications by themselves. Therefore, even for a single sonification it is unlikely that participants would spend more time than necessary on the training task. Both the number of participants and the number of items per experimental condition influence the power of linear mixed models (see Brysbaert & Stevens, 2018). Since the duration of the online study was supposed to be kept as short as possible, an increase in the number of participants per condition by using a repeated measures design was accompanied by a reduction in the number of items. In order to determine an optimal number of participants or items, a power analysis would be necessary. However, no appropriate data were available for the area of investigation of the present study. For the period of this study it was assumed that a sufficiently large number of subjects per condition could only be reached by using a repeated measures design. It was further assumed, that the variance with respect to the participants experience and practice in interpreting sounds is large, depending on their profession, working environment etc. and that consequently the variance between subjects would also be large with regard to the dependent variables of the listening test. For these reasons, the advantages of a repeated measures design were considered more important than those of a between subject design. Further covariates addressed the ability to evaluate different forms of sound, the professional involvement with a pulse oximeter and the musical background of the participants. Additionally, the training time was included as a covariate, since the duration of the training session was determined by the participants themselves. The dependent variables were the accuracy in identifying the seven SpO₂ ranges and the accuracy of absolute SpO₂ estimates.

2.3 Material

2.3.1 Sound stimuli

The sound files for the listening test were created in Pure Data. Due to requirements of the website *SoSci Survey* the sound files were further converted from a wav to a mp3 format via audacity. Each sound sample had a duration of 2500 ms. After an initial delay of 500 ms two pulses sounded at a speed of 60 bpm, each with a duration of 375 ms. For the part of the listening test, where participants had to identify different ranges of SpO₂, sound samples were created for all seven ranges of each sonification. Within the target range the sound of each sound sample corresponded to the mean oxygen saturation of the respective range. For example, the sound sample to indicate range 2 (94-95%) corresponded to an oxygen saturation of 94.5%. This was necessary because the sound of the sonification changes continuously within the target range. If the oxygen saturation lies at a transition point

between two ranges, it is practically impossible to assign the corresponding sound to one of the two ranges. For the psychoacoustic and the alternative sonification the sound does not change within range 1 and 7. The sound samples of these areas simply corresponded to a SpO₂ value of > 95% (range 1) or a SpO₂ value of < 90% (range 7). For the control condition, the sound for range 1 corresponded to an SpO₂ value of 96% and for range 7 to an SpO₂ value of 89%. Furthermore, the participants had to identify absolute SpO₂ values for the psychoacoustic sonification and the control sonification with an accuracy of one decimal place. The psychoacoustic sonification shows a continuous sound change in the range between 90- and 95% as a function of oxygen saturation. Therefore the absolute SpO₂ values had to lie between 90- and 95%. The interval that the Shepard tone of the psychoacoustic sonification goes through changes by a semitone for a change of 0.1% of the oxygen saturation. Accordingly it was of particular interest, whether such a change could be recognized by the participants. Sound samples were created for both sonifications, corresponding to SpO₂ values of 94.7, 93.4, 90.2, 91.6 and 94.2%. These values were chosen arbitrarily in order to include different areas of the target range with a small number of SpO₂ values. Sample sounds can be found under the following link: <https://t1p.de/h2b7>.

2.3.2 Visual stimuli

In the online experiment Figure 9 was used to illustrate the division of the oxygen saturation into seven ranges. The different ranges are separated by color, with each range being assigned to the corresponding SpO₂ area (e.g. 90-91%). Figure 10 shows a similar but simplified graphic used by the participants to identify a particular SpO₂ range in the listening test. Only the optimal range and the critical SpO₂ ranges are labelled. A specific range was selected by the participants by clicking with the mouse into the corresponding colour-coded area.

2.3.3 Demographic questionnaire

Participants were asked about their age, gender and profession (german: Alter, Geschlecht und Beruf). In addition participants were asked about other demographic aspects as possible predictors for the performance in the listening test. The first two items were designed to measure the ability to evaluate different forms of sound. Via the first item (*Sound-minutes*) participants were asked how many minutes per day they spend at work or in their free time on interpreting different forms of sound correctly. This includes musical, mechanical and other sounds (german: Wie viele Minuten am Tag haben Sie beruflich oder in Ihrer Freizeit damit zu tun, Klänge oder Geräusche richtig einzuordnen (bspw. Musik, maschinelle Geräusche etc.?). Via the second item (*sound-self-assessment*) participants were asked for a self-assessment of their ability to interpret different forms of sound (German: Wie geübt sind Sie

Figure 9. Division of the oxygen saturation into seven ranges. The optimum range lies between 90 - 95%. The corresponding saturation range is provided on the left of each colour-coded area. This figure was used as an illustration in the online experiment of the present study.

darin, Klänge oder Geräusche zu beurteilen?). The answer was given via a 7-point Likert-item, with only the extremes labeled at the end points of the scale (min = not at all, max = very well; german: min = gar nicht, max = sehr). The third (*pulse-oximeter*) and the fourth item (*pulse-oximeter-sound*) recorded how often the participants are professionally involved with a pulse oximeter. Via the third item participants were asked, how many minutes per day they use a pulse oximeter at work (german: Wie viele Minuten am Tag haben Sie in Ihrem beruflichen Alltag mit einem Pulsoximeter zu tun?). Via the fourth item participants were asked more specifically, how many minutes per day they are involved with the sound of a pulse oximeter at work (german: Wie viele Minuten am Tag haben Sie in Ihrem beruflichen Alltag mit den Klängen eines Pulsoximeters zu tun?). This item was added, as the clinical staff sometimes turns off the variable pitch or the alarm of a pulse oximeter to reduce noise. The last three items (four: *Music-years*, five: *Music-hours/week*, six: *Music-self-assessment*) were designed to measure the musical background of the participants. Specifically, participants were asked how many years of musical experience they have (german: Wie viele Jahre musikalischer Vorerfahrung haben Sie?) and how many hours they spend playing music per week (german: Wie viele Stunden machen Sie in der Woche Musik?). Finally, participants were asked about the level of their musical skills. The answer was given via a 7 point Likert item, where again only the end points were labelled (min = non musician, max = musician;

Figure 10. Division of the oxygen saturation into seven ranges. The optimum range lies between 90 - 95%. This illustration was used for the listening test of the present study. Participants were instructed to click with the mouse into the colour-coded area of the corresponding SpO₂ range.

german: min = Nichtmusiker, max = Musiker).

Why might these items be important for predicting the performance in the listening test? It is obvious that the experience with the sound of a pulse oximeter might also help in interpreting the sonifications in the listening test, at least for the sonification of a conventional pulse oximeter. Even if the sound of the pulse oximeter is turned off frequently, it might be of advantage to be familiar with the process of pulse oximetry, to be aware of the need to keep the oxygen saturation within a certain range and to be familiar with the sonification principle of translating data to sound. In addition, the musical background might explain some of the performance variance in the listening test. As explained in chapter 1.3, in case of the psychoacoustic sonification participants need to interpret the interval the Shepard tone goes through within one pulse. A musically trained person is used to evaluate the size of musical intervals and might thus interpret the psychoacoustic sonification more accurately. In general a musician is trained in evaluating the pitch of sounds, which is the central parameter of the sonifications of this study. However, musicians are not the only people, who are trained in interpreting sound. An obvious example is the clinical environment, where a lot of different alarm sounds convey information to the listener. Other examples might be a doctor, who interprets the breathing sound of a patient, in order to infer an underlying disease or a mechanic, who needs to evaluate the sound of an engine. Musicality is not sufficient to assess the ability to correctly interpret sounds. Therefore the items one and two, as described above, were added to the questionnaire.

2.3.4 Evaluation questionnaire

Each sonification was evaluated by the participants. Via the first item the participants were asked how well they could identify the saturation ranges in the listening test (german: Wie gut konnten Sie die Sättigungsbereiche (1-7) heraushören?). The answer was given via a 7 point Likert item, where only the end points of the scale were labelled (min = very bad, max = very well; german: min = sehr schlecht, max = sehr gut). The next three items were intended to address aesthetic aspects of the sonifications. All answers were given via a 7 point Likert item (min = disagree, max = agree; german: min = trifft nicht zu, max = trifft zu). The participants responded to the following statements: The sonification is acceptable in a clinical environment (german: Die Sonifikation ist in einer klinischen Umgebung vorstellbar); the sonification is pleasant to listen to (german: Die Sonifikation ist angenehm anzuhören); the sonification can run in the background for a long time (german: Die Sonifikation kann über einen langen Zeitraum im Hintergrund laufen). Apart from the perceived pleasantness, these items were intended to measure whether the sonification is perceived as suitable for pulse oximetry. In this respect the applicability in a clinical context as well as the possibility to listen to the sonification over a long period of time are important factors. All three sonifications of this study were evaluated by the participants, whereas the first item was not present for the alternative sonification. In addition the participants were asked whether aesthetic considerations should be given greater priority in the sound design of medical devices (german: Sollten ästhetische Aspekte beim Sound design medizinischer Geräte stärker berücksichtigt werden?). This item was added to determine the extent to which there is a need for more aesthetically pleasing sounds in the clinical environment. The perspective of clinically trained persons was of particular interest here.

2.4 Sonifications

This section mainly describes the implementation of the psychoacoustic sonification in Pure Data (Puckette, 2020). Background information on Pure Data comes from Puckette (2006). In Pure Data each partial of the Shepard tone was represented by an oscillator, which generated a pure sinusoid. The change of frequency for each partial was controlled by a metro object, which periodically send a "bang". The time interval between these "bangs" was used as an input parameter. A counter was incremented each time the metro object fired, whereby a periodic cycle from 0 to 72000 was created via a modulus operator. This value was then multiplied by a factor of 0.001 and then passed to the following exponential function:

$$f(x) = \sqrt[12]{2}^x. \quad (7)$$

The output of this function was then multiplied with the frequency of each partial. This way the frequency of the partials did rise or fall exponentially over a range of six octaves. Moreover, by using an exponential function with base $\sqrt[12]{2}$, two adjacent partials were always separated by an octave. With each pulse the period of the Shepard tone was set to the starting point, thus the frequency of the partial f_0 was set to 100 Hz, f_1 to $100 \text{ Hz} * \sqrt[12]{2}^{12}$, f_2 to $100 \text{ Hz} * \sqrt[12]{2}^{24}$ etc.. The time interval between the "bangs" send by the metro object was a function of the distance between the current SpO₂ value and the center of the target range (92.5% SpO₂). The distance was calculated as the absolute difference between the current SpO₂ value and a SpO₂ value of 92.5%. This absolute difference $|d|$ was than evaluated in the expression $0.0375/|d|$. The result was then passed to the metro object as the time interval between successive bangs. Thus with increasing distance from the center of the target range the time interval between successive bangs from the metro object got smaller and the speed of the Shepard tone increased. Note that the input for equation 7 was still linear due to the transformation via the metro object. If the distance from the center of the target range was increased by a constant value, this led to an input of the form $1/x$ for the metro object, where the number of "bangs" send by the metro object within a certain time interval was again a function of the form $1/x$. Here, the number of "bangs" within a pulse beat resulted from the duration of the pulse tone (375 ms) divided by the time interval between two successive "bangs". Thus the input for equation 7 was a linear function of the distance of the current SpO₂ value to the center of the target range. By changing the SpO₂ distance by 0.1%, the number of "bangs" send by the metro object within the time window of one pulse changed by a value of 1000. As the speed of the Shepard tone was set to 0 between 92- an 93% of SpO₂, $|d|$ in the expression $0.0375/|d|$ did never evaluate to 0. The amplitude of the Shepard tone was weighted by a bell shaped curve, as illustrated in Figure 11. The function of this curve was of the form

$$f(x) = e^{-x^2} \quad (8)$$

and further adapted to fit one period of the Shepard tone (six octaves). Each partial was simply multiplied continuously by the corresponding value of this function as they moved through the curve. The function was shifted to return a 1 for $x = 36$ (for a frequency of 800 Hz) and decreased exponentially on both sides of this maximum. As the sonification was supposed to get integrated in the sound design of a conventional pulse oximeter, a pulse like sound was created by using an envelope generator. The envelope can be described via the phases Attack, Decay, Sustain and Release (ADSR). In the present study, the amplitude in the attack phase increased to a value of 1 within 1 ms. Afterwards, the amplitude remained at a value of 1 for 375 ms, before dropping back to 0 within 1 ms. The decay phase was strictly speaking not present here.

Figure 11. Amplitude as a function of the frequency of 10 sinusoidal partials of a Shepard tone, which are represented by vertical lines. The partial tone f_0 is located on the very left and the partial tone f_N on the very right side of the envelope. Two neighbouring partials are always separated by one octave. The horizontal arrows indicate an increase or decrease in the frequency of the partials. The vertical arrows indicate possible sidebands for an FM synthesis of the central partial. Derived from Ziemer et al. (2017).

According to *Stanford Children's Health* (2020) the pulse rate of newborns lies typically between 120 bpm and 160 bpm. With a pulse rate of 160 bpm, the heart beats about 2.7 times per second. Thus, the sound of one pulse could have a duration of about 375 ms. Much shorter durations may be unfavorable, since below 300 ms the pitch strength decreases for sinusoidal sounds (see chapter 1.1.3). The duration of the pulse was therefore set to 375 ms (plus 1 ms attack and release phase each). As described in chapter 1.1.7 a sensation of roughness can be produced by frequency modulation (FM) synthesis. Relevant parameters are called carrier frequency, modulating frequency and frequency deviation (Chowning & Bristow, 1986, p. 46).

$$f_c = \text{carrier frequency}$$

$$f_m = \text{modulating frequency}$$

$$\Delta f = \text{frequency deviation}$$

Thereby the instantaneous frequency of the carrier frequency gets varied through the modulating frequency, whereas the rate of this variation is the frequency of the modulator. The modulation depth of the modulating wave is proportional to the peak frequency deviation of the carrier (Chowning, 1973). Figure 12 shows a section of a Pure Data patch of a FM synthesis used in the present study. Here a modulating frequency of 120 Hz and a modulation depth of 100 Hz was used. The ratio of Δf

Figure 12. Pure data patch of a FM synthesis, as implemented in the present study.

and f_m is called modulation index and is defined as

$$I = \frac{\Delta f}{f_m} \quad (9)$$

(Chowning & Bristow, 1986, p. 56). To describe the spectrum of the resulting signal it is sufficient to provide the ratio of carrier frequency and modulating frequency $c:m$ and the modulation index I . For a given ratio of c and m the potential frequency components are:

$$c \pm km$$

$$\text{for } k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n$$

where n is approximately $= I + 2$.

Accordingly the frequency components fall on either side of the carrier, by adding or subtracting integer multiples of m (Chowning & Bristow, 1986, p. 60). The group of frequencies below the carrier are referred to as lower side bands and the group of frequencies above the carrier accordingly as upper side bands (Chowning & Bristow, 1986, p. 61). Possible sidebands created by FM synthesis are illustrated in Figure 11 as red vertical arrows.

For the background noise within the target area, so-called pink noise, also called $1/f$ noise, was used. Pink noise has a constant power within one octave. The frequency is inversely proportional to the power density, such that the power increases by 3 dB per octave as the frequency decreases (Baxandall, 1968). In the present study pink noise was generated by an object from the *Cyclone library*, which is based on Max/MSP (Puckette & Zicarelli, 2020). Furthermore the pink noise was filtered by

a comb filter. Here a feedforward comb filter was used, which essentially consists of the direct signal and a delay line. A linear combination of direct and delayed signal forms the output of the filter. In Figure 13 the implementation of the feedforward comb filter in Pure Data is illustrated. The difference equation associated with the comb filter was defined as:

$$y(n) = x(n) + \alpha * x(n - M), \quad (10)$$

where $y(n)$ was the output, $x(n)$ the incoming signal, α a scaling factor and M the

Figure 13. Pure data patch of comb filtered pink noise. For the feedforward comb filter a coefficient of $\alpha = -1$ and a delay time of $1e-4$ ms were used.

length of the delay. In this study $\alpha = -1$ and $M = 1e-4$ ms.

Figure 14 shows the implementation of the control sonification in Pure Data. The weighting of the overtone amplitudes was done by ear, trying to avoid excess of high frequency energy. A pulse like sound with a duration of 375 ms was created by using the same temporal envelope as for the psychoacoustic sonification. For the alarm tone roughness was increased by FM synthesis. A modulating frequency of 100 Hz and a modulation depth of 100 Hz were used. Information on the implementation of the alternative sonification in Pure Data can be found in the appendix.

2.5 Procedure

In total, the online listening test comprised 34 pages, which can be found in the appendix. At the beginning, the participants were informed about the background and the procedure of the study. It was also pointed out that the data collection is anonymous, that the participant agrees to the collected data being used in the

Figure 14. Pure data patch used in the present study for the generation of the pulse tones of the conventional sonification.

context of this study and that the listening test can be stopped at any time. Participants were asked to use headphones or additional loudspeakers to complete the study. It was important to ensure that the sound samples could be heard by the participants without much effort. Next a questionnaire on the demographic background of the participants followed. The questions used there are described in chapter 2.3.3. The participants were then given background information that was important for conducting the listening test. More precisely, it was explained that for this study the oxygen saturation was divided into seven ranges, with the optimal range lying between 90- and 95%. This division into seven SpO₂ ranges was illustrated by a figure (see Figure 9). At this point it was also explained that in the listening test an answer was given by clicking into one of the seven ranges. To test this procedure, the participants were then asked to click into one of the ranges within the optimal range. By clicking, a cross appeared in the respective position. This task was to ensure that the participant understood the task and did not click anywhere arbitrarily. Moreover, this might already exclude the possibility of the questionnaire being answered by a computer program. The listening test consisted of two parts, one where participants had to identify SpO₂ ranges and another one, where absolute SpO₂ values had to be estimated. Each part was preceded by a short training. The listening test included the conventional and the psychoacoustic sonification, but not

the alternative sonification. The study was intended to take about 15 minutes to complete, which could not be realized with three different sonifications. The listening test (i.e. the identification of SpO₂ ranges and the estimation of absolute SpO₂ values) was performed first with either the conventional or the psychoacoustic sonification and afterwards with the remaining one, the order being randomly varied between participants. After the respective listening test was completed, the sonification was evaluated by the participants (see chapter 2.3.4 for details on the questionnaire).

The training for the task of identifying the seven SpO₂ ranges included a description of the design of the respective sonification and the possibility to listen to the sound-sample of each range (1-7). The participants could listen to the sound samples as they pleased, until they felt that they had become familiar with the principle of the sonification. An example question was then presented, as it was also used in the actual listening test. Here the participants were asked to listen to a sound-sample and then to click with the mouse into an illustration (see Figure 10), more precisely into the range they identified via listening to the sound-sample. Afterwards the listening test of identifying the seven SpO₂ ranges began. As for the sample question, the participants were asked to listen to a sound-sample and then to click into the identified range in the corresponding figure. There was also the possibility to correct the answer, as only the last placed cross was evaluated. In total the participants had to identify seven ranges per sonification, whereas the sound-sample of each range was presented only once. In general it would be desirable to use a larger number of trials per range, but this could not be realized, as the listening test was supposed to last about 15 min to complete. The sound-samples were presented in a random order, which differed between the first and the second sonification of the listening test. This way it was not possible to infer the corresponding range by remembering the order of the sound samples of the first sonification.

The subsequent task was about the estimation of absolute SpO₂ values. Again the listening test was preceded by a short training. Here participants were asked to watch a video with a duration of 52 seconds. In this video a slider moved from 89.9% in 0.1% steps to a value of 95.1% of SpO₂. Simultaneously, a recording of the corresponding sonification was audible, whereas the sound changed gradually and in synchrony with the 0.1% steps of the slider. This way the participants were supposed to get a feeling for the gradual change of the sounds. In the following listening test participants were asked to listen to different sound samples. In contrast to the task of identifying the seven SpO₂ ranges the sound of a sample could correspond to any SpO₂ value with one decimal place between 90 and 95%. After listening to the corresponding sample, the participants were asked to give an estimate of the oxygen saturation with one decimal place (e.g. 91.2%). In total the participants estimated five absolute SpO₂ values. As for the task of identifying the seven SpO₂ ranges, the

order of the SpO₂ values was different between the first and the second sonification to prevent any bias caused by remembering the order of the sound samples. Again the rather small number of estimates was due to the objective to keep the length of the study at about 15 minutes.

After the listening test was completed for both the conventional and the psychoacoustic sonification, the alternative sonification was presented. The sound design was described and the possibility was given to listen to the sound samples of the different ranges. As already mentioned, no listening test was carried out for this sonification and it was only evaluated in terms of its sound characteristics. On the last page the participants were asked whether they are interested in the results of this study and were referred to the author's e-mail address.

2.6 Data analysis

The data was prepared and analyzed with R (R Core Team, 2018). The package `lme4` (Bates, Mächler, Bolker, & Walker, 2015) was used for the calculation of linear mixed models (LMMs) and the calculation of generalized linear mixed models (GLMMs). The packages `car` (Fox & Weisberg, 2011) and `ggplot2` (Wickham, 2016) were used for the creation of all graphics and the package `PMCMR` (Pohlert, 2014) for multiple pairwise comparisons. Linear mixed models and generalized linear mixed models were calculated to examine the effect of the experimental manipulation on the dependent variables, while including all covariates of the study. The term mixed refers to the incorporation of both fixed and random effects. The levels of a categorial covariate can either be fixed and reproducible or they can represent a subgroup off all possible levels. In this case the categorial covariate is a random variable and its levels represent a random sample off all possible levels (Bates, 2010). In the present study the variable *sonification* is specified as a fixed effect and the variable *subject*, which refers to the participants, is specified as a random effect. It is straightforward to see that the participants in this study represent a subgroup of all potential participants. The specification of the variable *subject* as a random effect resolves the dependencies between multiple responses of each participant, as a different “baseline” is assumed for every individual subject. This results mathematically in the assignment of an individual intercept for each subject. Therefore, random effects are strictly speaking not parameters of the model, they can rather be understood as an extension of the error term (Winter, 2013).

At the observation level, the participants' responses regarding the seven SpO₂ ranges correspond to a binary random variable, i.e. it either takes a value of 1 or 0 for success or failure. The expected value of this variable represents the probability of correctly identifying a SpO₂ range. Therefore, the assumption of a normal distribution of the response vector was replaced by the assumption of a binomial distribution

and a GLMM was calculated. Absolute SpO₂ estimates were subtracted from the SpO₂ value of the corresponding sound sample. The absolute values of these difference were used for further statistical analysis. The demographic variables relating to pulse oximetry were excluded from the statistical analysis, as in the final data set only one subject reported to have experience with a pulse oximeter. Furthermore, self-assessments regarding the ability to judge sounds and the musical expertise were not used as covariates. As the responses given on these items correspond to an ordinal scale, there is no straightforward interpretation of the coefficients in a LMM. Moreover, there was a significant correlation between the variables *sound-minutes* and *sound-self-assessment* ($r = .35, p = .04$) as well as between the variables *music-hours/week* and *music-self-assessment* ($r = .51, p = .002$). In order to avoid multicollinearity of the predictors, only the variables *sound-minutes* and *music-hours/week* were used as covariates.

In order to examine the effects of the sonification type and other covariates on the corresponding dependent variable, linear mixed models were calculated, with the variable *subject* specified as a random effect. The type of the sonification (psychoacoustic or conventional) and additional covariates were specified as fixed effects. The covariates were the number of minutes participants spent per day interpreting different forms of sound (*sound-minutes*), the number of years of musical experience (*music-years*) and the number of hours participants spend playing music per week (*music-hours/week*). Finally, the duration (in seconds) the participants spent on the training for the respective sonification (*training-time*) was used as a covariate. The effects of the sonification type and the covariates as described above were analyzed separately for the dependent variables, i. e. for the identification of the SpO₂ ranges and the absolute SpO₂ estimates. The Akaike information criterion (AIC), the Bayesian information criterion (BIC), standard deviations of the random effects, coefficients and standard deviations of the fixed effects and confidence intervals were obtained by using the lme4 package (Bates, 2010). Confidence intervals (*CI*) were obtained via a likelihood profiling of the corresponding model (see Bates, 2010).

3 Results

3.1 Descriptive statistics

On average, participants identified the correct SpO₂ range in 58% ($SD = 31\%$) of all cases with the psychoacoustic sonification and in 46% ($SD = 25\%$) of all cases with the conventional sonification. Detection rates were calculated for each participant as the number of correct range identifications divided by the total number of items. For the calculation of the detection rates, a missing answer was evaluated as an incorrect response. Figure 15 illustrates the detection rates and Figure 16 illustrates the absolute SpO₂ estimates of each participant for the psychoacoustic and the conventional sonification. In addition, the average detection rates of the SpO₂ ranges 1-7 were calculated for the psychoacoustic and the conventional sonification respectively (see Table 1). On average, participants spent about 132 s ($SD = 98.64$ s) with the training prior to the actual listening test. The average training duration for the psychoacoustic sonification was approximately 128 s ($SD = 68.31$ s) and for the conventional sonification approximately 137 s ($SD = 122.72$ s).

Figure 15. Average detection rates of participants for the psychoacoustic and the conventional sonification.

Figure 16. Average absolute SpO₂ deviations of participants for the psychoacoustic and the conventional sonification.

Table 1

Mean (SD) of the detection rates of all seven SpO₂ ranges for the psychoacoustic and the conventional sonification

	Range 1	Range 2	Range 3	Range 4	Range 5	Range 6	Range 7
Sonification (psy.)	50% (50%)	40% (49%)	62% (49%)	81% (39%)	62% (49%)	37% (49%)	71% (45%)
Sonification (conv.)	68% (47%)	21% (42%)	37% (49%)	31% (47%)	37% (49%)	50% (50%)	81% (39%)

Note. Missing values were treated as an incorrect answer.

3.2 Probability of SpO₂ range identifications

Here the linear predictor η determines μ (the probability of success) via a link function. In the case of the binomial distribution, the linear predictor is equated with the logit of the positive responses (Bates, 2010). Values on the logit scale were retransformed via the inverse of the logit link function,

$$\mu = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\eta)}, \quad (11)$$

(Bates, 2010). As expected, the probability of identifying the correct SpO₂ range was significantly higher for the psychoacoustic relative to the conventional sonification ($p < .05$). All other fixed effects (standardized) were not statistically significant. However, all covariates showed a positive effect on the probability of identifying the correct SpO₂ range. The results are summarized in Table 2. For the psychoacoustic

sonification the probability of identifying the correct SpO₂ range was 60%, for an average participant with average values of all covariates. The probability to identify the correct SpO₂ range for the conventional sonification was 46%, again for an average participant with average values of all covariates. The chances to randomly guess the correct range were $1/7 \approx 14\%$. In addition further post hoc analyses were conducted. Initially it was of particular interest, if the participants were able to identify the SpO₂ value being within, below or above the target range. Therefore the responses were evaluated as correct, if ranges 1 and 7 were correctly identified, or if a range (2-6) within the target range was chosen for any SpO₂ value between 90-95%. As above, a generalized linear mixed model was calculated, where the subject was specified as random effect and the type of the sonification and all covariates (standardized) were specified as fixed effects. No significant main effect was found for the sonification type ($p > .05$). The results are summarized in Table 3. For the psychoacoustic sonification the probability of identifying the correct SpO₂ range was 90% for an average participant with average values of all covariates. For the conventional sonification the probability of identifying the correct SpO₂ range was 94%, again for an average participant with average values of all covariates. However, a significant effect was found for the training duration ($p < .05$), where the probability of correctly classifying the SpO₂ value as within, above or below the target range increased with an increasing training time. The main effect to be expected for the training time is illustrated in Figure 17.

Table 2

GLMM-estimates of the variance and standard deviation of the random effect and estimates for the coefficients, standard errors and CI's of the fixed effects for the probability to identify the correct SpO₂ range (logit-scaled)

Random effects	Variance	<i>SD</i>	
Subject	0.597	0.772	
Fixed effects	Coefficient	<i>SE</i>	95% <i>CI</i>
Intercept	0.414	0.203	[0.009, 0.826]*
Sonification (conv.)	-0.545	0.212	[-0.966, -0.131]*
Training-time	0.341	0.195	[-0.033, 0.746]
Sound-minutes	0.130	0.176	[-0.225, 0.495]
Music-years	0.199	0.222	[-0.241, 0.653]
Music-hours/week	0.267	0.195	[-0.124, 0.671]

Note. * $p < 5\%$; AIC = 570.5, BIC = 599.2.

Table 3

GLMM-estimates of the variance and standard deviation of the random effect and estimates for the coefficients, standard errors and CI's of the fixed effects for the probability to identify the SpO₂ value being within, above or below the target range (logit-scaled)

Random effects	Variance	SD	
Subject	0.343	0.585	
Fixed effects	Coefficient	SE	95% CI
Intercept	2.306	0.279	[1.809, 2.935]*
Sonification (conv.)	0.467	0.331	[-0.175, 1.130]
Training-time	0.776	0.395	[0.028, 1.600]*
Sound-minutes	0.223	0.223	[-0.201, 0.728]
Music-years	0.109	0.321	[-0.522, 0.770]
Music-hours/week	0.164	0.249	[-0.322, 0.709]

Note. * $p < 5\%$; AIC = 289.2, BIC = 317.9.

Figure 17. Identification of the SpO₂ ranges as a function of the amount of training time. The lines are scatterplot smoothed lines for the psychoacoustic and the conventional sonification. The shadows represent a 95% confidence interval.

It was also examined, if certain ranges could be identified more easily with the sonifications than others. Therefore, a GLMM was calculated separately for each sonification, whereby the variable *subject* was specified as random effect and the SpO₂ range as fixed effect. Multiple pairwise comparisons were calculated, by changing the reference level of the SpO₂ range and refitting the model each time. This way all 21 possible pairwise contrasts were evaluated. The results are summarized in tables 4 and 5. For the psychoacoustic sonification the probability of success was

significantly higher for range 4 than for ranges 1, 2 and 6 ($p < .05$). Furthermore, the probability of success was higher for range 7 than for ranges 2 and 6 ($p < .05$). For the conventional sonification the probability of success for range 1 was higher than for ranges 2, 4 and 5 ($p < .05$). In addition, the probability of success for range 7 was higher than for ranges 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 ($p < .05$).

Table 4

GLMM-estimates of multiple pairwise comparisons between SpO₂ ranges for the psychoacoustic sonification. Estimates of the variance and standard deviation of the random effect and estimates for the coefficients, standard errors and CI's of the fixed effects for the probability to identify the correct SpO₂ range (logit-scaled) are provided

Random effects	Variance	SD	
Subject	2.827	1.681	
Fixed effects	Coefficient	SE	99.762% CI
Range 1 vs Range 2	-0.586	0.629	[-2.571, 1.317]
Range 1 vs Range 3	0.919	0.651	[-1.027, 2.997]
Range 1 vs Range 4	2.198	0.725	[0.132, 4.634]*
Range 1 vs Range 5	0.786	0.634	[-1.119, 2.801]
Range 1 vs Range 6	-0.788	0.635	[-2.806, 1.120]
Range 1 vs Range 7	1.432	0.665	[-0.519, 3.593]
Range 2 vs Range 3	1.505	0.664	[-0.443, 3.660]
Range 2 vs Range 4	2.784	0.746	[0.687, 5.308]*
Range 2 vs Range 5	1.372	0.648	[-0.536, 3.469]
Range 2 vs Range 6	-0.202	0.636	[-2.185, 1.750]
Range 2 vs Range 7	2.018	0.683	[0.051, 4.269]*
Range 3 vs Range 4	1.279	0.731	[-0.877, 3.684]
Range 3 vs Range 5	-0.133	0.656	[-2.175, 1.884]
Range 3 vs Range 6	-1.707	0.672	[-3.899, 0.251]
Range 3 vs Range 7	0.513	0.679	[-1.553, 2.658]
Range 4 vs Range 5	-1.412	0.715	[-3.778, 0.678]
Range 4 vs Range 6	-2.986	0.756	[-5.549, -0.870]*
Range 4 vs Range 7	-0.766	0.724	[-3.117, 1.410]
Range 5 vs Range 6	-1.574	0.656	[-3.710, 0.345]
Range 5 vs Range 7	0.646	0.662	[-1.352, 2.750]
Range 6 vs Range 7	2.220	0.692	[0.237, 4.511]*

Note. * $p < 0.238\%$; AIC = 259.1, BIC = 286.3; Bonferroni adjustment method was used.

Table 5

GLMM-estimates of multiple pairwise comparisons between SpO₂ ranges for the conventional sonification. Estimates of the variance and standard deviation of the random effect and estimates for the coefficients, standard errors and CI's of the fixed effects for the probability to identify the correct SpO₂ range (logit-scaled) are provided

Random effects	Variance	SD	
Subject	1.594	1.262	
Fixed effects	Coefficient	SE	99.762% CI
Range 1 vs Range 2	-2.853	0.698	[-5.199, -0.892]*
Range 1 vs Range 3	-1.806	0.642	[-3.924, 0.048]
Range 1 vs Range 4	-2.250	0.657	[-4.436, -0.375]*
Range 1 vs Range 5	-1.892	0.640	[-4.010, -0.048]*
Range 1 vs Range 6	-1.219	0.622	[-3.247, 0.610]
Range 1 vs Range 7	0.968	0.719	[-1.154, 3.388]
Range 2 vs Range 3	1.047	0.639	[-0.850, 3.111]
Range 2 vs Range 4	0.603	0.640	[-1.329, 2.648]
Range 2 vs Range 5	0.961	0.633	[-0.923, 3.005]
Range 2 vs Range 6	1.634	0.636	[-0.215, 3.719]
Range 2 vs Range 7	3.821	0.797	[1.652, 6.606]*
Range 3 vs Range 4	-0.443	0.605	[-2.343, 1.396]
Range 3 vs Range 5	-0.086	0.594	[-1.924, 1.743]
Range 3 vs Range 6	0.587	0.589	[-1.194, 2.443]
Range 3 vs Range 7	2.775	0.739	[0.732, 5.356]*
Range 4 vs Range 5	0.358	0.560	[-1.471, 2.237]
Range 4 vs Range 6	1.031	0.599	[-0.751, 2.946]
Range 4 vs Range 7	3.218	0.757	[1.141, 5.868]*
Range 5 vs Range 6	0.673	0.586	[-1.091, 2.522]
Range 5 vs Range 7	2.861	0.739	[0.821, 5.448]*
Range 6 vs Range 7	2.187	0.717	[0.182, 4.683]*

Note. $p < 0.238\%$; AIC = 264.8, BIC = 292; Bonferroni adjustment method was used.*

3.3 Accuracy of absolute SpO₂ estimates (square-root)

A linear mixed model was calculated with the variable *subject* specified as random effect and the variables *sonification*, *music-years*, *music-hours/week*, *sound-minutes* and *training-time* specified as fixed effects. In order to meet the assumptions of normality and variance homogeneity of the residuals, a square root transformation was applied to the dependent variable (see figures 18 and 19). Contrary to expectations, the accuracy of absolute SpO₂ estimates did not differ significantly between the psychoacoustic and the conventional sonification (see Table 6).

Figure 18. QQ plots of theoretical and empirical quantiles of the residuals for examining normality. The dashed lines indicate a 95% confidence interval. (a) Absolute SpO₂ estimates; (b) Square root of absolute SpO₂ estimates.

Figure 19. Residual plots for (a) absolute SpO₂ estimates and (b) the square root of absolute SpO₂ estimates. The residuals are plotted as a function of the fitted values of the model.

In a further analysis, all SpO₂ estimates deviating by two standard deviations from the mean were excluded. With the remaining data set, likewise a linear mixed

model was calculated with the same fixed and random effects as described above. The results are summarised in Table 7. There was a significant effect for the variable *sonification*, whereby the SpO₂ estimates were more accurate for the psychoacoustic sonification than for the conventional sonification ($p < .05$). For the psychoacoustic sonification there was a mean deviation from the actual SpO₂ values of 0.69% and for the conventional sonification a mean deviation of 0.84%, in each case for an average participant and an average value of all covariates.

Table 6

LMM-estimates of the variance and standard deviation of the random effect and estimates for the coefficients, standard errors and CI's of the fixed effects for the accuracy of absolute SpO₂ estimates (square-root)

Random effects	Variance	SD	
Subject	0.032	0.178	
Fixed effects	Coefficient	SE	95% CI
Intercept	9.278e-01	6.621e-02	[0.813, 1.063]*
Sonification (conv.)	8.757e-02	4.649e-02	[-0.003, 0.180]
Training-time	2.305e-04	4.942e-04	[-0.001, 0.001]
Sound-minutes	-1.095e-04	3.760e-04	[-0.001, 0.001]
Music-years	-1.975e-03	2.642e-03	[-0.006, 0.003]
Music-hours/week	-1.954e-02	1.809e-02	[-0.055, 0.013]

*Note.** $p < 5\%$; AIC = 442.3, BIC = 472.4.

Table 7

LMM-estimates of the variance and standard deviation of the random effect and estimates for the coefficients, standard errors and CI's of the fixed effects for the accuracy of absolute SpO₂ estimates (square-root). Here absolute SpO₂ estimates two standard deviations above or below the mean were excluded from the analysis.

Random effects	Variance	SD	
Subject	0.027	0.165	
Fixed effects	Coefficient	SE	95% CI
Intercept	0.833	0.041	[0.754, 0.910]*
Sonification (conv.)	0.085	0.041	[0.004, 0.167]*
Training-time	0.007	0.034	[-0.059, 0.071]
Sound-minutes	-0.021	0.037	[-0.091, 0.049]
Music-years	-0.027	0.043	[-0.108, 0.054]
Music-hours/week	-0.046	0.039	[-0.119, 0.027]

*Note.** $p < 5\%$; AIC = 309.7, BIC = 339.3.

3.4 Evaluation

Seven-point Likert items were used for the evaluation of the sonifications. Via the first Likert-item (min = very bad, max = very well) the participants were asked how well they could identify the saturation ranges in the listening test. The responses are illustrated in Figure 20. The participants evaluated the identification of the seven SpO₂ ranges as being easier in case of the psychoacoustic ($Mdn = 3$) than in case of the conventional sonification ($Mdn = 2$). However, the result of a one-sided Wilcoxon signed rank test showed that this difference was not significant, $V = 130$, $p = .052$, $r = .24$.

Figure 20. Participants were asked, how well they could identify the saturation ranges in the listening test. Answers were given via a 7-point Likert-item (min = very bad, max = very well) for the psychoacoustic ($Mdn = 3$) and the conventional sonification ($Mdn = 2$).

All responses to the remaining items of the evaluation were given via a 7-point Likert-item (min = disagree, max = agree). A Friedman rank sum test gave a significant result, which showed that the three sonifications were evaluated as being differently suited for a clinical context ($\chi^2(2) = 7.81, p = .02$). The alternative sonification ($Mdn = 2$) was evaluated as less appropriate than the psychoacoustic ($Mdn = 3.5$) and the conventional ($Mdn = 3.5$) sonification. Here the participants responded to the following statement: The sonification is acceptable in a clinical environment (see chapter 2.3 for the original questions in German). Multiple pairwise comparisons were calculated with a post-hoc test after Conover (1999). The results are summarized in Table 8.

Table 8

Applicability of the sonifications in a clinical context. Effect sizes (r) for multiple post hoc comparisons are provided

	Sonification (psy.)	Sonification (conv.)	Sonification (alt.)
Sonification (psy.)	-	.17	.18***
Sonification (conv.)	-	-	.19***

Note. P-values were calculated by a post hoc test after Conover (1999); bonferroni adjustment method was used; * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Moreover, according to a Friedman rank sum test, participants evaluated the perceived pleasantness significantly different between the three sonifications ($\chi^2(2) = 11.37, p = .003$). Here the participants responded to the following statement: The sonification is pleasant to listen to. The psychoacoustic sonification was evaluated as less pleasant ($Mdn = 2.5$) than the conventional ($Mdn = 4.5$) and the alternative ($Mdn = 5$) sonification. Multiple pairwise comparisons were calculated with a post-hoc test after Conover (1999). The results are summarized in Table 9.

Table 9

Perceived pleasantness of the sonifications. Effect sizes (r) for multiple post hoc comparisons are provided

	Sonification (psy.)	Sonification (conv.)	Sonification (alt.)
Sonification (psy.)	-	.36***	.38***
Sonification (conv.)	-	-	.14

Note. P-values were calculated by a post hoc test after Conover (1999); bonferroni adjustment method was used; * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Lastly, the calculation of a Friedman rank sums test showed, that the sonifications were evaluated significantly different with regard to the statement, that the sonifi-

cation can run in the background over a long period of time ($\chi^2(2) = 11.52, p = .003$). The psychoacoustic ($Mdn = 2$) sonification was evaluated as less appropriate than the conventional ($Mdn = 4$) and the alternative ($Mdn = 3$) sonification. Multiple pairwise comparisons were calculated with a post-hoc test after Conover (1999). The results are summarized in Table 10.

Table 10

Applicability of the sonifications to a monitoring function. Effect sizes (r) for multiple post hoc comparisons are provided

	Sonification (psy.)	Sonification (conv.)	Sonification (alt.)
Sonification (psy.)	-	.36***	.27***
Sonification (conv.)	-	-	.01

Note. P-values were calculated by a post hoc test after Conover (1999); bonferroni adjustment method was used; * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Via the last item, participants were asked whether aesthetic aspects should be given greater consideration in the sound design of medical devices. Here the participants tended to agree with this statement ($Mdn = 5$).

4 Discussion

4.1 Probability of SpO₂ range identifications

The results show that the probability to identify the correct SpO₂ range was significantly higher for the psychoacoustic than for the conventional sonification. Thus the psychoacoustic sonification conveys information about the seven SpO₂ areas as defined in the present study more accurately than the conventional sonification. Yet, this result does not reveal if certain ranges could be identified particularly well by the participants. For instance, it is of special interest whether the SpO₂ ranges outside the target range could be identified. These aspects were examined in further post-hoc analyses (see below). Nonetheless, the results are promising, as the participants were able to identify the seven SpO₂ ranges significantly more accurately with the psychoacoustic sonification after a minimal amount of training. Hereby, they identified the SpO₂ ranges with the psychoacoustic sonification well above chance. This also suggests, that the psychoacoustic sonification may allow an improved monitoring of oxygen saturation in premature infants. However, the division of oxygen saturation into the seven SpO₂ ranges may not be meaningful from a clinical point of view. For instance, the information that the oxygen saturation is in the center of the target range might be irrelevant in a clinical context.

Furthermore, the influence of different covariates on the probability to identify the correct SpO₂ range was investigated. Although a positive effect on the dependent variable was observed for all of the covariates, none of them was significant. Other factors, which were not investigated here, may have been more relevant in this study. It can be assumed that the attention span in an online experiment is lower than in a laboratory experiment. It is thus not surprising that the duration of the training phase, which was determined by the participants themselves, was very short. As described above, the training included a text explaining the design of the sonification as well as the possibility to listen to the sound samples for the different SpO₂ ranges. On average, participants spent about two minutes each on the training sessions. For a very short training period, it may be particularly helpful to be able to quickly grasp new ideas or concepts. A person who is musically skilled or experienced in the interpretation of sounds can only have an advantage in the listening test if he or she understands the design of the sonification. Surprisingly, a higher training time did not lead to a better performance in identifying the SpO₂ ranges. However, other factors such as reading speed or text comprehension certainly are important as well. In addition, those participants who felt particularly insecure about the interpretation of sounds may have spent more time with the training than those who felt confident with the interpretation of the sonifications. Also, the test situation during an online experiment is much more difficult to control and possible sources of interference like

temporary distractions cannot be excluded.

In a post hoc analysis it was examined whether the sonifications communicate clearly and unambiguously to the listener, whether the oxygen saturation is within, above or below the target range. No significant effect on the probability of correctly identifying one of these three ranges was found for the variable *sonification*. In a clinical environment, as well as in the listening tests of other studies (e.g. Paterson et al., 2017), the alarm of a conventional pulse oximeter would be audible once when leaving the target range. Afterwards it is not audible anymore or would be turned off by the clinical staff. In contrast, the psychoacoustic sonification conveys continuously whether the current oxygen saturation is within or outside the target range. This can be an advantage, for example, if the alarm was missed by the listener. However, the listening test of the present study does not provide a continuity of the sonification. Here merely a snapshot with the duration of two pulse beats is used. This way the advantage of a sonification, which continuously provides the listener with information, disappears. For the conventional sonification, one has to determine the absolute pitch of the pulse tones to decide whether the oxygen saturation is below or above the target range. In contrast, for the psychoacoustic sonification, this information is conveyed via a rising or falling motion of the Shepard tone, which is a comparatively simpler coding. However, it is assumed that specifically for the conventional sonification the design of the listening test simplified the communication of this information. If one detected the alarm and determined the pitch of two pulse tones as being higher or lower than of those of the previous item, it had to be range 1 or range 7 respectively.

Further posthoc analyses indicated that the participants identified the different SpO₂ ranges of the psychoacoustic sonification with varying success. Range 4 was identified with a significantly higher probability than ranges 1, 2 and 6. It is not surprising that the participants found it particularly easy to identify range 4. The speed of the Shepard tone moving through its envelope is set to 0 in range 4, such that a tone with a constant pitch can be heard. Range 4 is the only range with a constant pitch of the pulse tones, allowing an unambiguous identification. In contrast, ranges 2 and 6 had to be determined via the direction of movement of the Shepard tone and the size of the tone interval the Shepard tone goes through within one pulse. While the direction of movement should be clearly identifiable, it is more difficult to determine the size of the respective tone interval. This requires some practice, which was only given to a very limited extent in this study. Thus, the pitch constancy in range 4 is possibly the sound characteristic of the psychoacoustic sonification that is most easily detected by the listeners. As described in chapter 1.1, the human auditory system is very sensitive to changes in pitch. In reverse, identifying a constant pitch among other tones of rising or falling tones is an easy task. The probability to identify range 7 was significantly higher than the probability to identify range 2 or

range 6. As described above, it is rather difficult to identify range 2 and range 6, whereas range 7 can be detected more easily by recognizing the direction of movement and the increased roughness of the Shepard tone as well as the discontinuation of the background noise. Nevertheless, the pairwise comparisons show an asymmetric structure, as the probability of identifying range 1 was not significantly higher than the probabilities of identifying ranges 2 and 6. There is no obvious explanation for this finding. Differences between the SpO₂ ranges were also found for the conventional sonification. As expected, the identification of the SpO₂ ranges 1 and 7 was most easily achieved by the participants. The probability of identifying range 1 was significantly higher than for ranges 2, 4 and 5 and the probability to identify range 7 was significantly higher than for ranges 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6. Thus, the alarm was perceived as a clear signal that the oxygen saturation was outside the target range. The SpO₂ ranges 1 and 7 were swapped in only 5 of 53 cases. Only the absolute pitch of the pulses provided information about the level of oxygen saturation relative to the target range. As mentioned above, it is assumed that the design of the listening test simplified the communication of this information.

4.2 Accuracy of absolute SpO₂ estimates

Although the absolute SpO₂ values were estimated more accurately with the psychoacoustic sonification than with the conventional sonification, the difference was not significant. However, when outliers were excluded, there was a significant difference between the sonifications, with SpO₂ estimates being more accurate with the psychoacoustic than with the conventional sonification. The results thus indicate that the psychoacoustic sonification can work continuously. This means that besides a change of acoustic properties in discrete steps to distinguish important SpO₂ ranges, an additional continuous change within certain SpO₂ ranges could provide the listener with very detailed and fine grained information about the current oxygen saturation. The results also support a combination of a stepwise and a continuous change of acoustic properties. In the study by Collett et al. (2019) tremolo and brightness were varied smoothly across SpO₂ values for the continuous sonification (see chapter 1.2.6.3). One estimates a relative magnitude for the size of a tone interval, as opposed to an absolute magnitude for the brightness of pulse tones (see Collett et al., 2019). A continuous change in acoustic properties might require a reference value to estimate SpO₂ values, which was not provided in the study by Collett et al. (2019). In the present study the Shepard tone is reseted to the starting point of its period, keeping the point of origin constant for every pulse tone. This reference value may have allowed the interpretation of a continuous change in the speed of the Shepard tone. Yet the accuracy of SpO₂ estimates differed only slightly between the psychoacoustic and the conventional sonification. Therefore it would be interesting if a longer training period could further improve the SpO₂ estimates

with the psychoacoustic sonification.

4.3 Evaluation

The evaluations regarding the difficulty of identifying the seven SpO₂ ranges did not differ significantly between the psychoacoustic and the conventional sonification. For both sonifications, more than half of the participants gave a response below the center (4) of the scale. Therefore, most of the participants felt uncertain interpreting the sonifications and found the task of identifying the SpO₂ ranges to be rather difficult. The listening test was most likely very challenging, especially since the task of the listening test was not practiced in advance. Furthermore, the participants reported having little experience with the interpretation of sounds. It is thus not surprising that only few participants perceived the identification of the SpO₂ ranges as an easy task.

The participants' ratings regarding the use of the sonifications in a clinical context differed significantly between the sonifications. The alternative sonification was significantly rated as less appropriate than the psychoacoustic and the conventional sonification. As described in chapter 1.3, the alternative sonification is based on samples of different musical instruments. The sound characteristics of this sonification thus differ greatly from those of sonifications typically found in a clinical context. In a clinical context, sample-based sonifications or natural sounds in general are unlikely to be heard. For most participants, the idea of listening to the sounds of various musical instruments in, for example, an intensive care unit was probably disconcerting. It is not clear whether this evaluation results from a perceived incompatibility of the alternative sonification with other, already existing sounds of a clinical environment. It is also possible that the participants perceived the use of musical instruments as inappropriate for the sonification of a pulse oximeter, due to the inherent quality of their sound. Also, the evaluations regarding the perceived pleasantness differed significantly between the sonifications. Listening to the psychoacoustic sonification was significantly evaluated as less pleasant than listening to the conventional or the alternative sonification. An essential difference between the psychoacoustic and the conventional sonification is the use of a changing as opposed to a constant pitch within individual pulses. For the listener, a continuous change of pitch may be more exhausting to listen to than a tone with a constant pitch (see Henkelmann, 2007). Nevertheless, listening to the alternative sonification was significantly rated as more pleasant than listening to the psychoacoustic sonification and no significant difference was found between the alternative and the conventional sonification. The familiarity with the instruments that were used for the alternative sonification may have led to a more positive evaluation of its tonal characteristics. In addition, the tones within the target range are plucked and thus decay quickly. These pulse tones may be more pleasant to listen to than those with a more constant

level.

The participants ratings regarding the statement that the sonification can run in the background over a long period of time differed significantly between the three sonifications. **The psychoacoustic sonification was significantly evaluated as less suitable than the conventional and the alternative sonification.** This reveals a pattern that is similar to the results concerning the perceived pleasantness. This result may not be surprising, as probably few people want to listen to a sonification that they find unpleasant over a long period of time. Finally, participants in the present study tended to agree with the statement, that it would be desirable to give greater consideration to aesthetic aspects when designing the sound of medical devices. However, there was only one person who reported having to deal with a pulse oximeter in his or her daily work. Overall, the participants probably had little experience with the typical sonifications of a clinical environment. Thus, the sample of the present study was rather unsuitable for a general evaluation of the sound design of current medical devices.

4.4 Limitations and prospects

Since the attention span during online studies is usually much lower than for a laboratory study, the duration of the listening test was aimed to take no more than 15 minutes. Within this time frame, participants had to perform a training and a listening test each with two different sonifications. While it is desirable when a sonification can be understood intuitively and therefore without investing much time, the potential of sonifications can only be explored through an appropriate training. Since most people also have little experience with sonifications, a training with a reasonable amount of time may be an important requirement for a successful interpretation. If the training is too short, the potential of the sonification may not be recognized in the case of a complex sound design or a complex listening task. Moreover, a reduced length of the listening test can have negative consequences, since the sensitivity of the applied statistical tests decreases with an decreasing number of items of a given experimental condition.

In the present study, 49 of 66 participants completed the experiment. Out of these 49 participants, 32 were eventually included in the statistical analysis, as the question of understanding implemented in the listening test was answered incorrectly by 17 participants. Overall, more than 50% of the participants were thus excluded from the initial data set. **This indicates that the listening experiment may have been very complicated and challenging to perform.** This is particularly problematic for an online study, whereas in a laboratory study there might have been fewer problems of understanding. Besides the comprehension task at the beginning of the experiment, it was not checked whether the participants had understood the respective task.

According to Hooley (2012) the reduced possibility of interaction in an online study can lead to difficulties in understanding instructions. It cannot be ruled out that a poor result in the listening test was caused by comprehension problems with the task or the respective sound design. In general, the researcher has less control over the experimental conditions in online experiments (Hooley et al., 2012). These include technical aspects such as the headphones, the computer, the internet browser as well as environmental sounds. Also, distractions of any kind may have influenced the results.

A generalization of the results to a listening situation in a clinical environment is only possible to a limited extent. In order to avoid possible problems of understanding, the experiment of the present study was designed as simple as possible. For each SpO₂ range to be identified, the participant listened to a three second excerpt of the respective sonification. This way the listening experiment was much easier to perform than with a longer presentation of the sonifications. In particular, the results cannot be generalized easily to a listening situation in which the sonification can be heard over a longer period of time. In addition, for each item the participants listened to the sound of the sonifications corresponding either to the mean value of one of the seven SpO₂ ranges or to one of the five arbitrarily determined absolute SpO₂ values (see chapter 2.3.1). In reality, oxygen saturation probably does not change that rapidly, so that the course of oxygen saturation may be easier to follow. In the present study participants were instructed to use headphones. This was to ensure that the sonification was clearly audible to all participants and to prevent masking by possible environmental noise. Headphones therefore offer an advantage over loudspeakers, since in the latter case listening is more easily disturbed by other sources of sound. Furthermore, one may assume that during the listening experiment the participants were in a relatively quiet environment and could concentrate solely on monitoring the oxygen saturation. However, these circumstances do not reflect the conditions in a clinical environment. Here one can expect a variety of background sounds, including sonifications of other medical devices. Typically, clinicians perform other tasks besides monitoring the patients oxygen saturation. For example, Paterson et al. (2016b) examined the extent to which a secondary task affects the ability to monitor the level of oxygen saturation. In another study (see Paterson et al., 2019), participants were asked to simultaneously monitor other vital parameters, such as heart rate, blood pressure and CO₂. In this way the applicability of the sonification can be tested under more realistic conditions. Finally, clinicians may interpret the sonification differently due to greater medical background knowledge. Nonetheless Paterson et al. (2019) found no differences in the detection rates for SpO₂ ranges between clinicians and non-clinicians. Thus, results from a sample of non-clinicians may be generalized to a sample of clinically trained persons.

With the exception of the variables related to the experience with a pulse oximeter,

all covariates as well as the age showed a large variance among the participants (see chapter 2.1). However, the heterogeneity of the sample with respect to some of these variables is relatively low. The majority of the participants stated that they had very little experience with the interpretation of sounds and that they were currently not engaged in musical activities. Therefore, the sample can not be assumed to be representative for those people, who would report a higher score on these variables.

Due to some of the limitations of the present study, a verification of the results under laboratory conditions would be desirable. This would allow a more realistic simulation of a continuously changing oxygen saturation. It would also be possible to provide an adequate training and to clarify possible questions of understanding. In view of a clinical application, the listening test should be performed under conditions that are more realistic for a clinical environment. In the future it would also be desirable to conduct a study with clinicians, including participants who have experience with a pulse oximeter.

Based on the post-hoc analyses of this study, one could consider to change the sound design of the psychoacoustic sonification. Results regarding the psychoacoustic sonification indicate that the probability of identifying the correct SpO₂ range is particularly high for range 4. Since the human auditory system is very sensitive to pitch changes, the identification of a sound with a constant pitch among other rising or falling tones is particularly effective. This circumstance can be further exploited for the design of the sonification. For example, a tone with a constant pitch could indicate that the oxygen saturation lies within an optimal range. A rising or falling tone could indicate a critical area above or below that range and the size of the interval that the Shepard tone passes through could indicate the distance to the target range. This might also increase the perceived pleasantness of the sonification. As described in chapter 3.4, listening to the psychoacoustic sonification was evaluated as less pleasant than listening to the conventional sonification. This may be due to the changing pitch within each pulse tone (see Henkelmann, 2007). If the pitch was constant within the target range, the psychoacoustic sonification might have been evaluated as equally pleasant and as equally suited to run in the background for a long period of time. In the current study a constant pitch indicated the center of the target range (92-93%) for the psychoacoustic sonification. If the oxygen saturation deviates from this range, the Shepard tone begins to rise or fall within a pulse tone. Thus, when leaving range 4, the tonal characteristics of the sonification change considerably. On the level of perception, this change could be interpreted as the occurrence of a new event and thus draw attention to the sonification. Yet it is not clear whether an oxygen saturation of 93.5% requires more attention than an oxygen saturation of 93%, as in both cases the oxygen saturation lies within the target range. Therefore, if the pitch remains constant within the optimum range, this might also improve the attentional mapping of the sonification. This alterna-

tive design proposed here does not change the basic structure of the psychoacoustic sonification. Instead, only the ranges 1-7 as defined in the present study would be assigned to different saturation ranges. Whether or not such a modification makes sense should be assessed by a clinically trained person. Depending on the situation, the requirements for the sonification might differ. The sonification could be used in an intensive care unit, in the delivery room or during surgery. The practical relevance of the information conveyed to the listener needs to be assessed by experts in the relevant field of application.

There was no significant improvement in estimating absolute SpO₂ values with the psychoacoustic sonification compared to the conventional sonification. Nevertheless, when absolute SpO₂ estimates of more than two standard deviations above or below the mean value were excluded from the statistical analysis, the estimates were more accurate with the psychoacoustic than with the conventional sonification. However, this needs to be verified in future studies. In particular, it would be interesting to see whether absolute SpO₂ estimates can be further improved with a longer and more intensive training. Moreover, it is not clear whether the scaling used for the psychoacoustic sonification represents an optimal choice. As described above, the size of the interval the Shepard tone passes through within a pulse tone changes by one semitone with a change in oxygen saturation of 0.1%. It was considered that the use of a certain musical interval for a specific change in oxygen saturation was a reasonable choice. The size of the interval is determined by the speed at which the Shepard tone moves through its envelope, since the duration of a pulse tone remains constant. Therefore, changing the interval by a semitone also changes the speed of the Shepard tone. It is not clear whether the gradual increase of the interval is perceived as approximately linear. The change in speed could cause a non-linear change in interval size on the perceptual level. Thus an optimal scaling may be determined in additional listening experiments.

In the present study, aesthetic aspects of the sonifications were examined, as they were considered particularly relevant in the context of a monitoring function. While the alternative sonification was evaluated as being more pleasant to listen to compared to the psychoacoustic sonification, it was perceived as less suitable for a clinical context. The results show that it is important to consider both the perceived pleasantness and the context of use when designing a sonification. In the future it would be useful to explore aesthetic aspects by comparing a large number of different sounds. The selected sounds could be evaluated according to their suitability for pulse oximetry and other aesthetic aspects. As the sonification is used in a clinical environment an evaluation by clinicians would be more informative than by non-clinicians. Moreover, the influence of predictors on the success in interpreting sonifications should be further investigated, whereas an optimal sample size could be calculated on the basis of the present study. Predictors of the success in inter-

preting sonifications are not limited to being used as control variables but also have practical relevance. For example, if a particular population has little practice or prior experience with the interpretation of sounds, a reduction in the complexity of the sonification or a longer training period may be necessary.

4.5 Summary

In the present study novel sonifications for the pulse oximeter were developed. During the development of the sonifications, special emphasis was placed on findings from the field of psychoacoustics. It was assumed that it would otherwise not be possible to convey information to the listener in a predictable way. The development of the sonifications has a specific context of application. As described above, Saustad and Aune (2013) recommend an oxygen saturation between 90- and 95% for prematurely born children. In reality, however, SpO₂ values often leave this target range when using conventional pulse oximeters. The sonifications developed in the present study are therefore intended to improve monitoring of premature infants by providing the listener with more accurate information on the level of oxygen saturation relative to a target range of 90-95%. Thereby it was tried to combine a stepwise with a continuous approach. Thus important thresholds are conveyed to the listener by a stepwise change, whereas a continuous change of psychoacoustic properties is intended to provide the listener with a very fine-grained resolution of SpO₂. These two objectives were addressed in an online listening experiment by two different tasks. In a first task participants were instructed to identify different SpO₂ ranges, whereas in a second task they had to estimate absolute SpO₂ values. A further aim of this study was to investigate the influence of individual determinants on the success in the listening test as well as aesthetic aspects of the sonifications. It was assumed here that both areas have a significant influence on the successful interpretation of a sonification. Overall, the results are very promising, as the participants were able to identify the seven SpO₂ ranges significantly more accurately with the psychoacoustic than with the conventional sonification after a minimal amount of training. Hereby they identified the SpO₂ ranges with the psychoacoustic sonification well above chance. In addition, the results indicate that absolute SpO₂ values can be estimated more accurately with the psychoacoustic than with the conventional sonification, whereby again only a minimal amount of training time was necessary. Here both sonifications showed a continuous change in their acoustic properties as a function of the current oxygen saturation. Thus the results also suggest that a combination of a stepwise and a continuous change in the acoustic properties of a sonification might be beneficial. As sonifications are used in a wide range of applications and disciplines it is difficult to establish general guidelines for the design of a sonification. However, the results of the present study show that the field of psychoacoustics provide a valuable basis for the sound design

of future sonifications. Last but not least it would be instructive to compare novel approaches for monitoring preterm infants (see e.g. Hinckfuss et al., 2016; Zestic et al., 2019) in a listening test in order to examine the advantages and disadvantages of different sound designs.

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Appendix A: Pure Data patches

Appendix B: Online questionnaire

Ein psychoakustisches Sounddesign für den Herzschlag

In meiner Masterarbeit möchte ich neue Verklänglichungen (Sonifikationen) für das Pulsoximeter miteinander vergleichen. Der Ton eines Pulsoximeters ist abhängig von der Pulsrate und der Sauerstoffsättigung. Es sollen hier 2 unterschiedliche Sonifikationen (Sonifikation A und Sonifikation B) getestet werden. Beiden gemeinsam ist ein pulsartiger Ton, der synchron mit dem Herzschlag zu hören ist. Die Sonifikationen werden zunächst vorgestellt. Anschließend erfolgt jeweils ein Training und ein Hörtest.

Die Datenerhebung erfolgt anonym und es können keine Rückschlüsse auf Ihre Person gemacht werden. Wenn Sie auf weiter klicken, stimmen Sie zu, dass wir die erhobenen Daten im Rahmen dieser Studie weiter verwenden. Sie können den Hörtest jederzeit abbrechen.

Verwenden Sie für die Durchführung der Studie bitte Kopfhörer oder zusätzliche Lautsprecher.

Weiter

Ein paar Fragen vorab..

Alter	<input type="text"/>
Geschlecht	<input type="text"/>
Beruf	<input type="text"/>

Wie viele Minuten am Tag haben Sie beruflich oder in Ihrer Freizeit damit zu tun, Klänge oder Geräusche richtig einzuordnen (bspw. Musik, maschinelle Geräusche etc.) ?

Wie geübt sind Sie darin, Klänge oder Geräusche zu beurteilen?

gar nicht sehr

Wie viele Minuten am Tag haben Sie in Ihrem beruflichen Alltag mit einem Pulsoximeter zu tun?

Wie viele Minuten am Tag haben Sie in Ihrem beruflichen Alltag mit den Klängen eines Pulsoximeters zu tun?

Wie viele Jahre musikalischer Vorerfahrung haben Sie?

Wie viele Stunden machen Sie in der Woche Musik?

Ich bin...

Nichtmusiker Musiker

Weiter

Die Sauerstoffsättigung wurde für diese Studie in 7 Bereiche unterteilt, wie in der folgenden Abbildung veranschaulicht. Der **Optimalbereich** liegt hier zwischen 90% und 95%. Die roten Bereiche liegen unter und über diesem Optimalbereich. Der dunkelgrüne Bereich (92-93%) kennzeichnet die Mitte des Optimalbereichs. In den folgenden Hörtests geht es um das Herausheören dieser 7 Bereiche der Sauerstoffsättigung.

Im Hörtest wird eine Antwort über das Anklicken einer der 7 Bereiche gegeben. Klicken Sie probeweise einmal mit der Maus in einen der Optimalbereiche, sodass ein Kreuz erscheint und fahren Sie anschließend fort.

Weiter

Vorstellung der Sonifikation B

In dieser Sonifikation ist synchron zu jedem Pulsschlag ein Ton mit konstanter Tonhöhe zu hören. Die Tonhöhe ist dabei abhängig von der Sättigungsfähigkeit. Je höher der Sättigungswert, desto höher ist auch die Tonhöhe. Beim Verlassen des Zielbereichs, sowohl oberhalb von 95% als auch unterhalb von 90%, erklingt ein Warnsignal in Form von drei kurzen Tönen.

In der folgenden Abbildung finden Sie auf der linken Seite zu jedem Bereich eine entsprechende Aufnahme, die Sie abspielen können. In jeder dieser Aufnahmen hört man zwei Pulschläge für einen Sättigungswert des ausgewählten Bereichs. Fahren Sie fort, sobald Sie sich mit der Sonifikation vertraut gemacht haben.

Bereich 1	<input type="range" value="0.02"/>	Bereich 1
Bereich 2	<input type="range" value="0.02"/>	Sehr hoch (> 95%)
Bereich 3	<input type="range" value="0.02"/>	(94-95%)
Bereich 4	<input type="range" value="0.02"/>	(93-94%)
Bereich 5	<input type="range" value="0.02"/>	Optimal- bereich (92-93%)
Bereich 6	<input type="range" value="0.02"/>	(91-92%)
Bereich 7	<input type="range" value="0.02"/>	(90-91%)
		Sehr niedrig (< 90%)

Beispielfrage

Im Folgenden beantworten Sie eine Beispielfrage, wie sie im Anschluss im eigentlichen Hörtest zu finden ist. Klicken Sie nach dem Abspielen der Aufnahme mit der Maus in den von Ihnen identifizierten Bereich. In diesem Bereich ist dann ein Kreuz zu sehen. Falls Sie unsicher sind, können Sie sich oben auch noch einmal die Aufnahmen anhören.

Sehr hoch	Optimalbereich	Sehr niedrig

Weiter

Frage 1

Klicken Sie in den Bereich, den Sie nach dem Abspielen der Aufnahme herausgehört haben. **Falls Sie Ihre Eingabe korrigieren möchten: Es wird immer nur das zuletzt gesetzte Kreuz gewertet.**

Weiter

Frage 2

Klicken Sie in den Bereich, den Sie nach dem Abspielen der Aufnahme herausgehört haben. **Falls Sie Ihre Eingabe korrigieren möchten: Es wird immer nur das zuletzt gesetzte Kreuz gewertet.**

Weiter

Frage 3

Klicken Sie in den Bereich, den Sie nach dem Abspielen der Aufnahme herausgehört haben. **Falls Sie Ihre Eingabe korrigieren möchten: Es wird immer nur das zuletzt gesetzte Kreuz gewertet.**

Weiter

Frage 4

Klicken Sie in den Bereich, den Sie nach dem Abspielen der Aufnahme herausgehört haben. **Falls Sie Ihre Eingabe korrigieren möchten: Es wird immer nur das zuletzt gesetzte Kreuz gewertet.**

Weiter

Frage 5

Klicken Sie in den Bereich, den Sie nach dem Abspielen der Aufnahme herausgehört haben. **Falls Sie Ihre Eingabe korrigieren möchten: Es wird immer nur das zuletzt gesetzte Kreuz gewertet.**

Weiter

Frage 6

Klicken Sie in den Bereich, den Sie nach dem Abspielen der Aufnahme herausgehört haben. **Falls Sie Ihre Eingabe korrigieren möchten: Es wird immer nur das zuletzt gesetzte Kreuz gewertet.**

Weiter

Frage 7

Klicken Sie in den Bereich, den Sie nach Abspielen der Aufnahme herausgehört haben. **Falls Sie Ihre Eingabe korrigieren möchten: Es wird immer nur das zuletzt gesetzte Kreuz gewertet.**

Weiter

Im Folgenden geht es um das Schätzen von Sättigungswerten auf einer kontinuierlichen Skala. Bisher gab es für jeden der sieben Bereiche einen spezifischen Ton, dem der Mittelwert des jeweiligen Bereichs zugrunde lag. In dem folgenden Video nimmt die Sauerstoffsättigung von 89.9% bis 95.1% in 0.1%-Schritten stetig zu. Schauen Sie sich das Video an, um ein Gefühl für die schrittweise Veränderung der Töne zu bekommen.

In der folgenden Aufgabe sind mit einer Nachkommastelle Sättigungswerte zwischen und einschließlich 90% und 95% möglich. Dazu hören Sie eine Aufnahme wie im bisherigen Hörtest. Anschließend geben Sie mit einer Nachkommastelle (bspw. 91.2%) eine Schätzung der Sauerstoffsättigung an.

Weiter

Wert 1

Geben Sie mit einer Nachkommastelle (bspw. 91.2%) eine Schätzung der Sauerstoffsättigung an.

% -0.02

Weiter

Wert 2

Geben Sie mit einer Nachkommastelle (bspw. 91.2%) eine Schätzung der Sauerstoffsättigung an.

%

Weiter

Wert 3

Geben Sie mit einer Nachkommastelle (bspw. 91.2%) eine Schätzung der Sauerstoffsättigung an.

%

Weiter

Wert 4

Geben Sie mit einer Nachkommastelle (bspw. 91.2%) eine Schätzung der Sauerstoffsättigung an.

%

Weiter

Wert 5

Geben Sie mit einer Nachkommastelle (bspw. 91.2%) eine Schätzung der Sauerstoffsättigung an.

%

Weiter

Vorstellung der Sonifikation A

Innerhalb des Zielbereichs (90-95%) ist ein durchgehendes Hintergrundrauschen zu hören. Wird der Zielbereich verlassen (Bereich 1 oder 7) fällt das Rauschen weg und der Ton erhält eine stärkere Rauigkeit. Im Bereich 4 ist ein konstanter Ton zu hören. Oberhalb von Bereich 4 steigt der Ton an, unterhalb davon fällt er ab. Je größer dabei der Abstand von Bereich 4 ist, desto stärker ist der Anstieg beziehungsweise Abfall der Tonhöhe.

In der folgenden Abbildung finden Sie auf der linken Seite zu jedem Bereich eine entsprechende Aufnahme, die Sie abspielen können. In jeder dieser Aufnahmen hören man zwei Pulschläge für einen Stützwert des ausgewählten Bereichs. Fahren Sie fort, sobald Sie sich mit der Sonifikation vertraut gemacht haben.

Beispielfrage

Im Folgenden beantworten Sie eine Beispielfrage, wie sie im Anschluss im eigentlichen Hörtest zu finden ist. Klicken Sie nach dem Abspielen der Aufnahme mit der Maus in den von Ihnen identifizierten Bereich. In diesem Bereich ist dann ein Kreuz zu sehen. Falls Sie unsicher sind, können Sie sich oben auch noch einmal die Aufnahmen anhören.

Frage 1

Klicken Sie in den Bereich, den Sie nach dem Abspielen der Aufnahme herausgehört haben. **Falls Sie Ihre Eingabe korrigieren möchten: Es wird immer nur das zuletzt gesetzte Kreuz gewertet.**

Weiter

Frage 2

Klicken Sie in den Bereich, den Sie nach dem Abspielen der Aufnahme herausgehört haben. **Falls Sie Ihre Eingabe korrigieren möchten: Es wird immer nur das zuletzt gesetzte Kreuz gewertet.**

Weiter

Frage 3

Klicken Sie in den Bereich, den Sie nach dem Abspielen der Aufnahme herausgehört haben. **Falls Sie Ihre Eingabe korrigieren möchten: Es wird immer nur das zuletzt gesetzte Kreuz gewertet.**

Weiter

Frage 4

Klicken Sie in den Bereich, den Sie nach dem Abspielen der Aufnahme herausgehört haben. **Falls Sie Ihre Eingabe korrigieren möchten: Es wird immer nur das zuletzt gesetzte Kreuz gewertet.**

Weiter

Frage 5

Klicken Sie in den Bereich, den Sie nach dem Abspielen der Aufnahme herausgehört haben. **Falls Sie Ihre Eingabe korrigieren möchten: Es wird immer nur das zuletzt gesetzte Kreuz gewertet.**

Weiter

Frage 6

Klicken Sie in den Bereich, den Sie nach dem Abspielen der Aufnahme herausgehört haben. **Falls Sie Ihre Eingabe korrigieren möchten: Es wird immer nur das zuletzt gesetzte Kreuz gewertet.**

Weiter

Frage 7

Klicken Sie in den Bereich, den Sie nach Abspielen der Aufnahme herausgehört haben. Falls Sie Ihre Eingabe korrigieren möchten: Es wird immer nur das zuletzt gesetzte Kreuz gewertet.

Weiter

Im Folgenden geht es um das Schätzen von Sättigungswerten auf einer kontinuierlichen Skala. Bisher gab es für jeden der sieben Bereiche einen spezifischen Ton, dem der Mittelwert des jeweiligen Bereichs zugrunde lag. In dem folgenden Video nimmt die Sauerstoffsättigung von 89.9% bis 95.1% in 0.1%-Schritten stetig zu. Schauen Sie sich das Video an, um ein Gefühl für die schrittweise Veränderung der Töne zu bekommen.

In der folgenden Aufgabe sind mit einer Nachkommastelle Sättigungswerte zwischen und einschließlich 90% und 95% möglich. Dazu hören Sie eine Aufnahme wie im bisherigen Hörtest. Anschließend geben Sie mit einer Nachkommastelle (bspw. 91.2%) eine Schätzung der Sauerstoffsättigung an.

Weiter

Wert 1

Geben Sie mit einer Nachkommastelle (bspw. 91.2%) eine Schätzung der Sauerstoffsättigung an.

%

Weiter

Wert 2

Geben Sie mit einer Nachkommastelle (bspw. 91.2%) eine Schätzung der Sauerstoffsättigung an.

%

Weiter

Wert 3

Geben Sie mit einer Nachkommastelle (bspw. 91.2%) eine Schätzung der Sauerstoffsättigung an.

%

Weiter

Wert 4

Geben Sie mit einer Nachkommastelle (bspw. 91.2%) eine Schätzung der Sauerstoffsättigung an.

%

Weiter

Wert 5

Geben Sie mit einer Nachkommastelle (bspw. 91.2%) eine Schätzung der Sauerstoffsättigung an.

%

Weiter

Eine alternative Sonifikation C

Aus Zeitgründen soll diese Sonifikation nur vorgesehlt und in Bezug auf ihre klanglichen Eigenschaften evaluiert werden. In Bereich 4 ist ein konstanter Gitarrenton zu hören. Oberhalb von Bereich 4 steigt der Ton an, unterhalb davon fällt er ab. Je größer dabei der Abstand von Bereich 4 ist, desto stärker ist der Anstieg beziehungsweise Abfall der Tonhöhe. In Bereich 2 und 3 ist eine ansteigende gezipfte Geige und in Bereich 1 eine ansteigende Piccoloflöte zu hören. In Bereich 5 und 6 ist eine abfallende Gitarre und in Bereich 7 ein abfallender Kontrabass zu hören.

In der folgenden Abbildung finden Sie auf der linken Seite zu jedem Bereich eine entsprechende Aufnahme, die Sie abspielen können. In jeder dieser Aufnahmen hört man zwei Pulsschläge für einen Schrittwert des ausgewählten Bereichs. Fahren Sie fort, sobald Sie sich mit der Sonifikation vertraut gemacht haben.

<p>Bereich 1 (Piccoloflöte + stark ansteigend)</p>			
<p>Bereich 3 (Geige gezippt + wenig ansteigend)</p>			
<p>Bereich 5 (Gitarre + wenig abfallend)</p>			
<p>Bereich 7 (Bass gestrichen + stark abfallend)</p>			

Bereich 1

(> 95%)

Bereich 2

(94-95%)

Bereich 3

(93-94%)

Bereich 4

(92-93%)

Bereich 5

(91-92%)

Bereich 6

(90-91%)

Bereich 7

(< 90%)

Die Sonifikation ist in einer klinischen Umgebung vorstellbar.

trifft nicht zu trifft zu

Die Sonifikation ist angenehm anzuhören.

trifft nicht zu trifft zu

Die Sonifikation kann über einen langen Zeitraum im Hintergrund laufen, ohne zu stören.

trifft nicht zu trifft zu

Eigene Kommentare (optional)

Sollten ästhetische Aspekte beim Sounddesign medizinischer Geräte stärker berücksichtigt werden?

trifft nicht zu trifft zu

Weiter

Vielen Dank für Ihre Teilnahme!

Für Nutzer von SurveyCircle (www.surveycircle.com): Der Survey Code lautet: LLZ1-2JR4-VNJF-7T7W
Wenn Sie Interesse an den Ergebnissen dieser Studie haben, schreiben Sie gerne eine E-Mail an: sebastian.schwarz-1@studium.uni-hamburg.de

Möchten Sie in Zukunft an interessanten und spannenden Online-Befragungen teilnehmen?

Wir würden uns sehr freuen, wenn Sie Ihre E-Mail-Adresse für das SoSci Panel anmelden und damit wissenschaftliche Forschungsprojekte unterstützen.

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Die Teilnahme am SoSci Panel ist freiwillig, unverbindlich und kann jederzeit widerrufen werden.
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Sie können das Browserfenster selbstverständlich auch schließen, ohne am SoSci Panel teilzunehmen.

Erklärung

Ich versichere an Eides statt durch meine eigenhändige Unterschrift, dass ich die beiliegende Arbeit selbstständig und ohne fremde Hilfe angefertigt und alle Stellen, die wörtlich oder annähernd wörtlich aus Veröffentlichungen entnommen sind, als solche kenntlich gemacht habe. Außerdem habe ich mich keiner anderen als der angegebenen Literatur, insbesondere keiner im Quellenverzeichnis nicht benannten Internet-Quellen, bedient. Diese Versicherung bezieht sich auch auf zur Arbeit gehörige Zeichnungen, Skizzen, bildliche Darstellungen etc. Ich bestätige, dass die Arbeit noch nicht in einem anderen Prüfungsverfahren eingereicht wurde. Weiterhin entspricht die eingereichte schriftliche Fassung der Arbeit der Fassung auf dem eingereichten elektronischen Speichermedium. Mit der späteren Einsichtnahme in meine Hausarbeit erkläre ich mich einverstanden/nicht einverstanden.

Datum

Unterschrift